

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D8.2

Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS

WP8 – T8.2

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 2

Technical reference

Work package	WP8 - Concepts and toolboxes
Task	T 8.2 - Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks
Dissemination level ¹	PU
Lead Beneficiary/ Responsible AE	AUTH
Contributing Participants	AUTH (EL), SLU (SE), INSERM (FR), INRAE (FR), VITO (BE), AU (DK), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), UniLU (LU), UU-IRAS (NL), VUA (NL), WR (NL), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), DGS (PT), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), ORU (SE), IVL (SE), SLV (SE), UMU (SE), EA (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL)
Responsible author(s)	Denis Sarigiannis/AUTH/sarigiannis@auth.gr Spyros Karakitsios/AUTH/spyrosk@auth.gr
Co-authors	Achilleas Karakoltzidis (AUTH, karakoltzidis.achilleas@gmail.com), Lutz Ahrens (SLU, lutz.ahrens@slu.se), Katrin Vorkamp (AU, kvo@envs.au.dk), Nikiforos Alygizakis (NKUA, nalygizakis@chem.uoa.gr), Tuulia Hyötyläinen (ORU-MTM, tuulia.hyotylainen@oru.se), Pawel Rostkowski (NILU, pr@nilu.no), Roland Kallenborn (NMBU, roland.kallenborn@nmbu.no), Anna Kärrman (ORU-MTM, Anna.Karrman@oru.se), Mario Carere (ISS, mario.carere@iss.it), Georgios Niarchos (SLU, georgios.niarchos@slu.se), Magnus Engwall (ORU-MTM, magnus.engwall@oru.se), Linda Irene Bengtström (AU, lben@envs.au.dk), Maria Larsson (ORU-MTM, maria.larsson@or, Olivier Taboureau (INSERM, olivier.taboureau@paris7.jussieu.fr), Patric Andersson (UMU, patrik.andersson@umu.se), Javad Mottaghipisheh (SLU, javad.mottaghipisheh@slu.se), Gunnar Thorsen (IVL, gunnar.thorsen@ivl.se), Linda Önnby (IVL, Linda.onnby@ivl.se), Karine Audouze (INSERM, karine.audouze@u-paris.fr), Emilio Benfenati (IRFM, emilio.benfenati@marionegri.it), Fotini Tzoumanika (EFET, ftzoumanika@gmail.com), Zoi Mousia (EFET, zmousia@efet.gr), Niki Maragou (UOA, nmarag@agro.uoa.gr), Emma Schymanski (UniLU,

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 3

	<p>Emma.schymanski@uni.lu), Julien Parinet (ANSES, julien.parinet@anses.fr), Alexander Badry (UBA, Alexander.Badry@uba.de), Nicole Bandow (UBA, nicole.bandow@uba.de), Jean-Philippe ANTIGNAC (INRAE, jean-philippe.antignac@oniris-nantes.fr), Georges KASS (EFSA, Georges.KASS@efsa.europa.eu), Maciej Stepnik (QSAR LAB, m.stepnik@qsarlab.com), Marija Sollner (UL FFA, marija.sollner@ffa.uni-lj.si), Kirsten Baken (VITO, kirsten.baken@vito.be), Bouzembrak, Yamine (WR, yamine.bouzembrak@wur.nl), Sanna Lignell (SLV , sanna.lignell@slv.se), Sims Kerry (EA, kerry.sims@environment-agency.gov.uk), Matej Ivartnik (NIC, matej.ivartnik@nijz.si), Joan Grimalt (CSIC, joan.grimalt@idaea.csic.es), Leonards P.E.G. (VUA, pim.leonards@vu.nl), Thanasis Papageorgiou (AUTH, thanasispapageorgiou15@gmail.com), Anthoula Chatzimpaloglou (AUTH, anthoula_xatz@hotmail.com), Catherine Gabriel (AUTH, katerinagabriel89@gmail.com)</p>
Reviewers external to WP	<p>Marja Lamoree/VU/ marja.lamoree@vu.nl Jean-Philippe Antignac /INRAE/jean-philippe.antignac@inrae.fr</p>
Due date of deliverable	30/04/2023
Actual submission date	25/01/2024

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 4

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
1	06 June 2023	Denis Sarigiannis/AUTh Spyros Karakitsios/AUTh And co-authors	First draft of D8.2
2	02 July 2023	Marja Lamoree, VU, Jean-Philippe Antignac	<p>Understandably, many authors have contributed to this document. It needs a thorough final redaction/revision to ensure smooth reading, consistent spelling and terminology, and avoidance of repetition.</p> <p>For other deliverables, the abbreviation EBM should consistently be used for Effect Based Monitoring, not for effect based methods. Please check the whole document.</p> <p>European legislation and guidelines should be represented in their correct format, not a collection of single words.</p> <p>Include house dust as sentinel matrix for human exposure in the indoor environment.</p> <p>Include wastewater based epidemiology as an early warning for community wide exposure assessment.</p> <p>Section 5.2 needs more background and elaboration.</p> <p>The way forward needs to be addressed in a concluding remarks section, preferably including some concrete actions (e.g. reach out to other tasks, projects for input)</p> <p>How will the EWS be accessible? Please add.</p>
3	22 January 2024	Denis Sarigiannis/AUTh Spyros Karakitsios/AUTh	Final version of D8.2

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 5

Abstract

The current deliverable describes the PARC Early Warning System concept and the various sources of data that will be used to support its implementation. PARC EWS will support the need for a systematic, permanent, and coordinated EWS in place at EU level focusing on emerging chemical risks to the environment, to ensure that EU policies address emerging chemical risks early. PARC EWS will follow a continuously evolving approach, will support early identification of risks, and continue to evolve during the course of the PARC project, including the advances in exposure analysis, EDA, chemical analysis including suspect and non-targeted analysis, and hazard assessment data and methodologies delivered within PARC and beyond. This will also address the heterogeneity of data that will have to be evaluated and translated into signals. The overall approach of the PARC EWS is stepwise, entailing the steps of (a) screening and filtering of signals; (b) confirmatory check for legislation and measures; (c) acquisition of information and signal amplification. One more primary element that an Early Warning System should have, is the ability to exchange broad pieces of information and alerts to a wide range of stakeholder, including policy makers, regulators, public and communities and interact with government officials, emergency responders, and community leaders. All of the above data search would be supported by AI based algorithms for data and text mining. However, considering the difficulties for collating scarce data and mainly the generation of new data, a key component for the successful implementation of this step is the Rapid Response Mechanism (WP2) established in PARC, who could act as a focal point/data collection/specific task assignment hub for filling data gaps.

Overall, the PARC early warning system will have a comprehensive scope that includes coverage of a wide range of chemical risks, geographic areas, sectors, data sources, stakeholders, and time. This will ensure that it can detect and respond to potential risks in a timely and effective manner and provide decision-makers with the information they need to mitigate or prevent the impact of chemical risks on communities and the environment.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 6

List of Abbreviations

3-MCPD	3-monochloropropane-1,2-diol
AAC	Administrative Assistance and Cooperation
ADI	Applicability Domain Index
ADME	Adsorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion
AI	Artificially Intelligence
AMAP	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme
AnMAP	Antarctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme
AOPs	Adverse Outcome Pathways
AQI	Air Quality Index
ARBs	Antibiotic Resistant Bacteria
ARGs	Antibiotic Resistant Genes
BfG	German Federal Institute of Hydrology
BN	Bayesian Network
CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
CECs	Contaminants of emerging concern
CheBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest
CIS	Common implementation strategy
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
CMR	Carcinogenic, Mutagenic and Reprotoxic
CRED	Criteria for Reporting and Evaluating ecotoxicity Data
DNAPLs	Dense Non-Aqueous Liquids
DRBF	Deep Radial Basis Function
DSFP	Digital Sample Freezing Platform
EA	Environment Agency
EBTs	Effect-Based Trigger
EC	European Commission
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 7

EDA	Effect Directed Analysis
EDCs	Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEC	European Economic Community
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMA	Elementary Model Analysis
EMEP	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme
EMPODAT	Chemical Occurrence Database
EMRISK	Emerging Risks Project
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
EQS	Environmental Quality Standards
EREN	Emerging Risk Exchange Network
ETCs	European Topic Centres
EU	European Union
EWS	Early Warning System
FBA	Flux Balance Analysis
FCMs	Food Contact Materials and Articles
FFN	Food Fraud Network
GAPS	Global Atmospheric Passive Sampling
GC	Gas Chromatography
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GE	Glycidyl fatty acid esters
HABs	Harmful Algal Blooms
HBM	Human biomonitoring
HPLC	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography
HRMS	High Resolution Mass Spectrometry
HTS	High-Throughput Screening
ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass-Spectrometry
InChIKey	IUPAC International Chemical Identifier

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 8

IoT	Internet of Things
IPECHEM	Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring
KEs	Key Events
LC	Liquid Chromatography
LLM	Large Language Models
LSTM	Long-Short Term Memory
MCA	Metabolic Control Analysis
MIE	Molecular Initiating Events
ML	Machine Learning
MoA	Mode of Action
MS2	Tandem Mass Spectrometry
NAMs	New Approach Methodologies
NDS	Database System
NERCs	New and Emerging Risks of Chemicals
NFAs	National Food Authorities
NFPs	National Focal Points
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
NN	Neutral Network
NTS	Non-targeted screening
PAHs	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
Pas	Pyrrolizidine alkaloids
PBPK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic
PBPK/TK	Physiology Based Pharmacokinetic or Toxicokinetic
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PCBs	Polychlorinated Biphenyls
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
PERC	Perchloroethylene
PEWS	Prioritisation and Early Warning System
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 9

PMT	Persistent, Mobile and Toxic
POPs	Persistent organic pollutants
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
qAOP	quantitative AOP
QSAR	Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship
RASFF	Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed
RASFF	Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RIMV	Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
RIVM	Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
RNNs	Recurrent Neural Networks
SES	Socio-Economic Status
SLE	Suspect List Exchange
sles	Sodium Laureth Sulfate
sls	Sodium lauryl Sulfate
SOPs	Standard Operating Procedures
SPM	Suspended Particulate Matter
STADG-ER	Stakeholder Discussion Group on Emerging Risks
SusDat	Substance Database
SVHC	Substances of Very High Concern
SVMs	Support Vector Machines
TOMPs	Toxic Organic Micro Pollutants
UBA	German Environment Agency
UK	United Kingdom
US	United States
VOCs	Volatile Organic Compounds
vPvM	very Persistent and very Mobile
WBE	Wastewater-Based Epidemiology
WFD	Water Framework Directive

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 10

WSN Wireless Sensor Networks

Key Words

Early Warning Systems, Prioritisation, Monitoring methods, Modelling tools, Human biomonitoring, non targeted screening (NTS), Suspect Screening (SS), , Chemical databases

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 11

Table of contents

1. Introduction	13
1.1 The need for an EWS for chemicals	13
1.2 Aims and scope of PARC EWS	13
2 Existing EWS for chemical risks	15
2.1 Case studies and Applications of Existing EWS	15
2.2 Existing EWS systems	16
2.2.1 Overview of European EWS	16
2.2.2 National Scale EWS	17
2.2.3 Other EWS	20
2.3 Identification of knowledge gaps and recommendations for a PARC EWS	20
3 PARC EWS concept	22
3.1 Key concept of the PARC EWS	22
3.1.1 Methodological description of the PARC EWS	22
3.1.2 Links to policy	25
3.2 Computational integration	29
4 References	31
5 ANNEX I: Methodological elements to support an EWS	47
5.1 Monitoring tools	47
5.1.1 Role of monitoring tools in EWS	47
5.1.2 Matrices for monitoring	48
5.1.3 Additional methods	58
5.2 Modelling tools	62
5.2.1 Role of modelling tools in EWS	62
5.2.2 Environmental fate models	65
5.2.3 Exposure models	66
5.2.4 PBPK/TK models	68
5.2.5 Systems biology models	69
5.2.6 Bioinformatics	72
5.2.7 QSARs models	73
5.2.8 Text Mining tools	76

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 12

5.2.9	Other AI models	77
6	<i>ANNEX II: Sources of information for the PARC EWS</i>	82
6.1	Sources outside PARC	82
6.1.1	NORMAN network	82
6.1.2	RIVM/ECHA work on NERCs	84
6.1.3	EFSAs Emerging Risk Exchange Network (EREN)	84
6.1.4	Human biomonitoring data	85
6.1.5	Information Platform on Chemicals Monitoring (IPCHEM)	86
6.1.6	Monitoring in polar regions	87
6.1.7	European Environmental Agency	88
6.1.8	National monitoring networks	88
6.1.9	National food authorities	89
6.1.10	Social media	90
6.2	Sources inside PARC	90
6.2.1	WP2 on prioritization	90
6.2.2	WP3 by SF and IB consultation and synergies outside PARC	90
6.2.3	WP4 on environmental, HBM and exposure data	90
6.2.4	WP5 on hazard assessment	90
6.2.5	WP6 on risk estimates and IATA	91
6.2.6	WP7 on available data and analyses	91
6.2.7	WP8 on computational methods (Task 8.3)	91

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 13

1. Introduction

1.1 The need for an EWS for chemicals

There is a growing number of chemicals in use by society resulting in exceeding planetary boundaries for novel chemical entities (Persson et al., 2022). Despite progress in chemical regulation, the assessment of chemicals of emerging concern entering the environment and posing potential risks to human health and the environment remains incomplete. This growing challenge underlines the need for an Early Warning System (EWS), to inform both monitoring and management activities on those chemicals which pose the greatest risk.

An EWS allows for the identification and tracking of potential risks associated with the use of chemicals. This can help to mitigate the risks associated with exposure, prevent negative health outcomes and widespread environmental impacts. An EWS can help to identify potentially problematic chemicals at an early stage before they are widely used or distributed. It can also help assessing and addressing exposure-related risks in vulnerable populations, contributing to better protection and management strategies. In addition, it can also facilitate the development of appropriate regulations and policies to control the use of these chemicals and help to ensure that they are used safely and responsibly.

An EWS uses a combination of data sources to provide early alerts to decision-makers. Data sources can be related to computational tools that monitor newly available literature as well as tools that can use the available data to provide an early insight into potential problems. The PARC EWS will be able to scan all compartments across the environment-food-human continuum. Environmental matrices include air, water, sediment, wastewater, soil, groundwater, and biota. Food will be also considered as a major external exposure source. The EWS will also cover various human matrices including urine and serum, and both abiotic and biotic transformation products. Thus, the PARC EWS will be able to analyze empirical data from multiple sources or mine text from the literature applying natural language processing. Real time information and alerts provided by EWS will play a crucial role in an efficient risk assessment and management of chemical pollution.

1.2 Aims and scope of PARC EWS

PARC EWS will constitute a tool for regulators for identification of potential chemical risks using various data sources. Early and fast detection is crucial and supports the mitigation and prevention of the impact of a hazard on communities and the environment. These alerts and warnings should be clear, concise, and easy to understand, and should include information on the nature of the hazard and the areas likely to be affected. Last, but not least, it should be flexible and adaptable, and cost-effective, to ensure that it can respond to changing conditions and provide the best possible protection to communities and the environment.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 14

The scope of an EWS refers to the range of hazards and risks that it is designed to detect and respond to. Firstly, the tool shall have a wide chemical applicability domain covering from small organic chemicals and inorganic species to larger molecular units. Secondly, geographic coverage enacts the need for a global tool. This means it should be able to detect hazards in different regions, including urban and rural areas, and in different countries. This can be achieved by using modelling tools that will be described extensively in next chapters. Apart from modelling tools, monitoring matrices will enable 360 degrees hazard detection, meaning that the EWS will be able to detect risks originating from numerous sectors such as air quality or wastewater monitoring.

One more primary element that an EWS should have, is the ability to exchange comprehensive information and alerts to a wide range of stakeholders, including policy makers, regulators, public and communities and interact with government officials, emergency responders, and community leaders. Overall, an EWS should have a comprehensive scope that includes coverage of a wide range of hazards, geographic areas, sectors, data sources, stakeholders, and time. This will ensure that it can detect and respond to potential risks in a timely and effective manner and provide decision-makers with the information they need to mitigate or prevent the impact of hazards on communities and the environment. Critical will also be continues development, validation, and maintenance of the EWS for improved performance, robustness and sensitivity.

To conclude, the primary goal of the EWS is to identify early on chemicals that could potentially be characterized as hazardous, leading to adverse effects. It also aims to identify the circumstances in which exposure to different chemicals could lead to a harmful effect to humans and the environment. A wide scope ensures that risks are detected and addressed promptly, enabling decision-makers to reduce hazards impact on communities and the environment.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 15

2 Existing EWS for chemical risks

2.1 Case studies and Applications of Existing EWS

Within government agencies and organizations that include representatives from governmental authorities and academic institutions in different countries, there is increasing awareness of the need for early identification of chemicals of concern and providing early warnings on new, potential and emerging chemical risks. For example, the Netherlands has developed an approach to identify New and Emerging Risks of Chemicals (NERCs) (Bakker et al., 2017; Palmen, 2015). In Sweden the Toxicological council presented an initial development of an EWS based on a computational data curation methodology followed by hazard screening using existing estimation platforms (Bruks et al., 2021), and in the UK, the Environment Agency (EA) has developed over recent years a Prioritisation and Early Warning System (PEWS) for the UK (Cartwright et al., 2021). The concepts for these programmes to develop approaches for identifying signals and EWS are similar, although differ in scope, scale and methodology employed.

There is a need to select generic indicators for the early identification of emerging hazards to food safety, preventing the latter from becoming real risks. Changes in these indicators are signals that may require follow-up (Kleter & Marvin, 2009). Apart from those generic indicators for emerging hazards that have been identified in literature, early signals from two data sources (science and food safety authorities) preceding the emergence of food safety incidents have been collected, categorized, and evaluated (van de Brug et al., 2014). More specifically the results of the European Food Safety Authority's (EFSA) Emerging Risks Project (EMRISK) and the food safety early warning framework of Kleter and Marvin were combined with the existing meat processing companies putting forward an early warning indicator system (Xiong et al., 2020). In another application case (dairy supply), drivers of change and other indicators representing signals preceding many months the detection of a food safety risk were used for a fully automated system for data collection, processing, analysis, and warning (Liu et al., 2022). Milk was also used as a case study to provide evidence that the deep radial basis function (DRBF) model has a better function for the complex food safety inspection data (Geng et al., 2017).

Drinking water is specifically useful for early warning prioritization and monitoring of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) (Baken et al., 2018), as well as a variety of chemical and microbial contaminants (Hartmann et al., 2020). The screening of environmental samples such as: wildlife taxa for CECs (Badry et al., 2022); aquatic environment for pharmaceuticals and personal care products-PPCPs (Richardson et al., 2005), biomarkers (Khan et al., 2020) and long-chain chlorinated paraffins (Yuan et al., 2022) were also used, while performing retrospective analysis on high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) data, the establishment of a global emerging contaminant early warning network was proposed for aqueous

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 16

environmental samples (Alygizakis et al., 2018). Such an advanced method (HRMS) was proposed for human samples in order to detect CECs providing an early warning support to policy (Pourchet et al., 2020).

2.2 Existing EWS systems

2.2.1 Overview of European EWS

In Europe, several national and international approaches to identify upcoming chemical threats already exist, with different levels of maturity. Existing EWS in Europe are categorized according to the system that they refer to: a) Environment, b) Workers and c) Consumers (European Commission et al., 2017).

Environment

There are two systems that are operating towards the identification and management of New or Emerging Risks of Chemicals in the environment. The first one is the NORMAN network (2016), which is an international network of reference laboratories, research centers and related organizations for the monitoring of emerging substances. This network is collecting information and monitoring data about the effects and the hazardous properties of the chemicals. One of the analytical approach that is being used from NORMAN network is suspect/non-targeted screening (NORMAN, 2016). The second example is the (national) system operating under the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), which uses online media monitoring, expert consultation, and non-target screening for the identification of new or emerging risks (Palmen, 2016).

Workers

Only one method identifying and prioritizing New Emerging Chemicals is presented by Palmen and Verbist (2015); this is considered as a “disease first” method. The main limitation of this approach is the long response time between the exposure and the effect. The use of biomarkers for the main endpoints or the detection of more sensitive effects may be considered. In analogy, there is no “exposure first” method for workers, except for occupational human biomonitoring to provide a partial overview of chemical exposure in the workplace. Vigilance systems in place in several EU countries regarding adverse outcomes from occupational exposure to chemical and biological stressors could be considered as type of an early warning system (an example is represented by the RNV3P system in France in the case of allergic reactions to new chemicals in the workplace). Still, such vigilance systems are “disease first” approaches, since they are based on the identification of adverse health outcomes in the workplace, which are then associated with specific chemical exposures to new and emerging chemicals of concern.

Consumers

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 17

An interesting process for environmental scanning regarding food related consumer products is implemented by EFSA (EFSA, 2014b; EFSA, 2014a). The EFSA system is identifying emerging hazards and new exposure pathways aiming at anticipating a possible risk or event preventing it. This system seems to be anticipatory, rather than responsive, and differs from the rapid alert systems such as Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF), where notifications are triggered after consumer complaints or mainly after controls (RASFF, 2022). The EFSA process could contribute to an early warning system eventually. Most of the time the system identifies weak signals; some of them proceed in the process through data collection till they acquire enough shared information with additional data sources and systems to support an early warning.

What should be emphasized is that the systems that exist to date are based on “effect based” or “disease first” methods and/or “exposure first” methods. What is currently lacking is a comprehensive platform that identifies chemical threats by applying different approaches to collect these signals across the EU. Cooperation and further exchange of information on new emerging chemicals between the EU members is mandatory. What else is needed on the EU level is an integral approach to cover identification, find more evidence, and propose the appropriate risk management measures, for a non-toxic environment.

2.2.2 National Scale EWS

2.2.2.1 United Kingdom

The UK Environment Agency, in response to a commitment in its 25 Year Environment Plan to consolidate monitoring and horizon scanning, has established a national scale EWS for the United Kingdom. This system is referred to as the PEWS for CECs. An overview of the PEWS is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A diagram of the PEWS system.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 18

Nominations to the system can be made by anyone with a chemical of concern, by emailing PEWS@environment-agency.gov.uk. Insights from the scientific literature are fed in from systematic checks of specific journals on a daily basis. Environmental monitoring data is fed into the system, as are insights from horizon scanning.

Once information has been included in PEWS, it goes through an initial sifting step, looking at high level information such as use in the UK, high level hazard information and whether there is public interest in the substance. At this stage, substances may be parked and recorded if demonstrated that they do not warrant further attention. However, as many chemicals do require further investigation, the next stage is a screening step with review of exposure and hazard information for a substance. Screening results in a prioritisation score of 1-4 for the water compartments (surface waters including freshwater and marine, and groundwaters), and for soil, biota and sediment substances based on a refined set of criteria either flag for further consideration or not.

A screening to potential intervention step is included to determine whether the substance warrants further regulatory focus. Potential intervention options include initiating new action, maintaining the delivery of existing actions, further monitoring of a substance, or parking and reviewing a substance once further evidence is available. The system has the potential to expand and get implemented across the UK, and is currently under consideration by the respective administrations for Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland.

2.2.2.2 Germany

The German Environment Agency (UBA) has launched the project “Ad-hoc assessment for water monitoring of the future” in September 2022 to develop assessment options for non-target screening (NTS) data. The project will provide hazard screening tools to quickly identify and prioritise CECs in water bodies. For this purpose, UBA is setting up advisory boards with experts from authorities, industry and research to harmonise assessment approaches and advise the project. An essential part of the project is the development of curated lists of marketed substances and their uses including the underlying chemical legislation (e.g., REACH chemicals, biocides, plant protection products, pharmaceuticals), use volumes, and their fate and effects data. Thereby the project will support the risk assessment of potentially problematic substances with chemical exposure data from major water bodies in Germany. Moreover, the project also aims to develop innovative approaches for identifying frequently occurring chemical mixtures and novel assessment approaches.

The central element of the project is the NTS Portal, which the German Federal Institute of Hydrology (BfG) is developing on behalf of the UBA. It contains federal and state NTS measurement data from water monitoring in Germany. The NTS portal will be continuously improved so that it becomes the central point of contact for overarching questions on

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 19

substances in chemicals and environmental legislation. To achieve this goal, assessment-relevant properties, e.g. physico-chemical parameters and (eco-)toxicological endpoints from other, already existing databases (e.g. NORMAN Database System; <https://www.norman-network.com/nds/>) will be integrated into the NTS Portal. In line with the risk and hazard assessment, data on persistence and accumulation in food webs are also considered to establish an EWS for CECs.

Standardised samples from Environmental Specimen Banks play an important role in the project as they can be used for the analysis of state-of-the-art analytical methods. Time series of standardised suspended particulate matter (SPM) samples from the German ESB were already analysed using Liquid Chromatography (LC) – HRMS based workflows. In addition to HRMS data, annotated features for a growing number of compounds are also available in the NTS Portal. Those features were identified using a reference library consisting of tandem mass spectrometry (MS²) spectra and retention times of reference compounds (≙Database Assisted Screening). First attempts using KI-methods (supervised machine learning) have been implemented on the HRMS data to (1) prioritise features in a time-series with distinct temporal trends and (2) to detect seasonal patterns that might be relevant for chemicals that are released in batches into the environment. The German ESB is directly involved in the development of an EWS at UBA and is planning to also contribute samples to PARC 8.2

2.2.2.3 Sweden

The Swedish system for early warning is organized under the Toxicology Council which is an expert organization with representatives from Swedish authorities, working in the area of chemicals regulation, and academic expertise covering relevant scientific disciplines related to chemical risks. The Toxicology Council identifies and evaluates signals of potential new and emerging chemical hazards and reports their observations to the Coordination Group for New Toxicological Chemical Threats, SamTox. SamTox includes the Directors General from eight Swedish authorities and the purpose of this organization is to ensure a structure for rapid and systematic transfer of information and knowledge between responsible authorities and other actors, as well as cooperation in the event of a serious chemical threat. The members of the Toxicological Council contribute with scientific and regulatory monitoring of the environment from their respective authorities and research areas.

Each member of the Toxicological Council is responsible for identifying chemical risk signals within their area of expertise. The Council jointly analyses and prioritizes the signals in order to focus on areas that should be further evaluated, e.g., by gathering additional data. The Council takes a joint decision on which signals to regard as new potential emerging chemical risks or known but not sufficiently managed risks. Observations of potential risks are reported annually to SamTox and the council meets four times per semester. In addition, the

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 20

observations have been used in prioritization processes for introduction of new chemicals in screening and monitoring campaigns. The system is overall expert based but has in recent years funded a pilot project on the development of a more systematic EWS. This system is computer based and strives to enable automatic data curation and semiautomatic hazard scoring and filtering for identification of NERCs.

2.2.3 Other EWS

Further activities on the developments of EWS are currently conducted at other European agencies, including those in Norway, Switzerland, and Austria. Additionally, valuable insights into EWS can be obtained from regional initiatives, such as those focused on the Arctic region.

We propose the distribution of a questionnaire among European competent authorities. This questionnaire aims to combine and harmonise the efforts for developing a European EWS for chemicals risks.

2.3 Identification of knowledge gaps and recommendations for a PARC EWS

EWS for chemical risks are designed to identify and respond to potential threats posed by chemicals, posing environmental and human health risks (European Commission et al., 2017). Through a literature review (EUROSTAT, 2020; Moisés & Kunguma, 2023; NORMAN, 2016; Palmen, 2016; UN, 2006; UN, 2012), a number of gaps were identified regarding the effectiveness of currently existing EWS.

One of the gaps in EWS is the lack of data, meaning data collection and management, including lack of comprehensive data on the properties and effects of emerging chemicals, and paucity of data on their regulatory status and sales figures. This influences the assessment of the risk of a chemical and the decisions on how to respond to a potential hazardous.

A second gap is the lack of integration of data coming from different sources. Data used in an EWS originate from a variety of sources, such as monitoring networks, academic institutions, and government agencies. The effective integration of these sources can be challenging due to differences in format, data type, temporal and spatial resolution, accuracy and access rights.

To achieve effective data integration, communication and collaboration are needed. Shortcomings in communication and collaboration between those involved in chemical risk assessment, such as different stakeholders in chemical management of industry, government, and the society at large, may inhibit the development and implementation of an effective EWS. Furthermore, the ability of the different parties involved in the functioning of an EWS is something that can affect overall system effectiveness. What we have found to be primarily

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 21

lacking is the capacity to analyse efficiently the different data types, to support interpretation of the results and of course the communication of the results to the correct parties and stakeholders.

Finally, an effective EWS in Europe requires sustained funding and resources, as well as expert personnel, high throughput equipment, and appropriate infrastructure.

Based on these gaps, the following recommendations to further develop an EWS for chemical occurrence, fate and effects will be addressed in task 8.2 of PARC:

- Management systems should be developed and implemented for the effective collection, storage, and analysis data from different sources.
- Enhanced communication and cooperation among the different parties should be promoted to facilitate the sharing of necessary information among stakeholders involved in emerging chemical risks and the development of integrated EWS.
- By identifying the appropriate workflow, the growth of technical capacity for the parties involved in EWS can be achieved. This can be accomplished through trainings on data collection, analysis, and interpretation of the upcoming results.
- Sustained funding and resources should be ensured for the development and maintenance of the EWS. This should include investment in specialized personnel, high throughput equipment, and appropriate infrastructure.
- The effectiveness of the EWS should be regularly reviewed and evaluated, considering not only its functionality for experts but also its accessibility for citizens. This would no doubt help on the identification of new areas of improvement and adjust as needed.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 22

3 PARC EWS concept

3.1 Key concept of the PARC EWS

3.1.1 Methodological description of the PARC EWS

PARC EWS will support the need for a systematic, permanent, and coordinated EWS in place at the EU level focusing on identification of emerging chemical risks for humans and the environment, to ensure that EU policies address those early.

The PARC EWS, follows the current recommendations of the “Pilot of an EU EWS for emerging chemical risks to the environment” (EU, 2021), including a two-tier system for addressing both (a) ‘priority central needs’ and (b) more comprehensive and complex features, up to automated signal generation.

This continuously evolving approach will support early identification of risks taking stock of and exploiting advances in exposure analysis, chemical analysis, EDA, computational methodologies, and hazard assessment approaches within PARC and beyond. It will also address the heterogeneity of data that will have to be evaluated and translated into signals.

The PARC EWS is visionary and aims at reaching a holistic AI-driven system using multiple sources of information covering exposure and effect data, and other indicators of risk to identify potential emerging risk chemicals. It will be based on contemporary experimental and computational data and know-how in the field. The system will use existing data bases and models on exposure and effects, open-source information including grey literature, patent information and product and material content data, computational platforms including read-across and QSAR tools, and data from EDA and non-targeted screening projects. The system aims at moving from expert judgments and manual horizon scanning towards an AI-driven, broad scanning and fully automatic precautionary system. However, in initial phases of operation of the system, simplicity and user-friendliness will be driving to support stakeholder activities. The overall approach of the PARC EWS is stepwise, entailing (a) screening and filtering of signals; (b) confirmatory check for legislation and measures; (c) acquisition of information and signal amplification; The processes in each step and the criteria to move from one step to the next one, are described below:

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 23

Figure 2. PARC EWS conceptual representation

Screening and filtering of signals: In the first step of the EWS, experimental data from multiple sources covering exposure and hazard are fed into an AI-driven risk signal scoring system. In this first step, data is complemented with other sources of NERC signalling including data on novel use of chemicals in new sectors, e.g., production of batteries, solar cells, 3D-printing, or other emerging techniques, or consumer data that together with chemical presence in materials and products could indicate potential exposure. That could also be early information on novel hazard measures including omics or other toxicological assays data or trigger information that could be picked up using e.g., targeted or non-targeted text mining. Early signals could also be picked up from EDA studies and non-targeted analytical screening activities. Criteria to move to the next step, starting from the ones proposed by the EU Pilot EWS (EU, 2021), include:

- Newly identified risk or hazardous property of substances

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 24

- New group of substances on the market, which might be a potential alternative for existing groups subject to measures
- Groups of substances at research and development phase and/or not yet on the market
- Groups of substances which might already be known to exist but recently, seems to be commercially used at larger scale than in the past.
- New type of use of already known (hazardous) substances
- Shift of use within a group of substances (e.g. from long chains to short chains)
- Group of substances detected in the environment or human biosamples to a level that might indicate effects
- Substance detected in the environment or human samples in increasing number of samples and/or media
- Substance detected in the environment or human samples in increasing concentrations over time
- Clear relation between occurrence and effect, using multiple lines of evidence, including NAMs

Confirmatory check for legislation and measures; the confirmatory check for legislation and measures, should include whether there is sufficient signal coverage by the current EU chemical legislation, such as REACH or specific chemical product legislation, such as biocides and pharmaceuticals. If the signal is adequately covered by existing relevant legal framework explanations should be investigated such as lack of compliance with legislation or difficulties to enforce the legislation.

Acquisition of information and signal amplification; If a signal passes the confirmatory check, highlighting the fact that current legislative measures do not address properly this signal, additional information related to exposure and hazard properties could be added. That may include using additional data sources and models. Suitable monitoring and modelling methods are explicitly described in this deliverable, such as:

- Re-analysis of existing environmental and human samples for the targeted compound(s) in order to check for occurrence and magnitude
- Data from NAMs approaches for additional data on hazard potency
- Additional information on the potential risks may stem by EBM
- Use of multimedia models to deliver PEC at various media and potential exposure scenarios based on production volumes
- Translate concentrations in environmental media, food items and consumer products into exposure estimates and use of PBTK models for estimating internal exposure
- Use of bioinformatics tools and systems biology models and AOPs to better understand hazard

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 25

All of the above data search would be supported by AI based algorithms for data and text mining. However, considering the difficulties for collating scarce data and mainly the generation of new data, a key component for the successful implementation of this step is the Rapid Response Mechanism (WP2) established in PARC, which could act as a focal point/data collection/specific task assignment hub for filling data gaps.

3.1.2 Links to policy

3.1.2.1 Current regulatory frameworks

The chemical legislation in the EU is generally considered strict in comparison to the chemical legislation in many other countries. The precautionary principle is a basis for chemical legislation in the EU, implying that decision-makers should adopt precautionary measures if the scientific evidence is uncertain about risk for human health or the environment.

Reduction of risks and impacts from chemicals and their mixtures that potentially can jeopardize the environment and human health, is addressed in several regulatory frameworks. Taken together, the regulatory frameworks cover a wide group of chemicals and include various parts of the society and the environment, including natural and engineered compartments. For instance, there is Ambient Air Quality directive (European Commission, 2008a), prioritized substances in water e.g., Water Framework directive (European Commission, 2000), Marine strategy framework directive (European Commission, 2008b), groundwater directive (European Commission, 2006) and the Watch list substances in surface water and groundwater (European Commission, 2018a), and prioritized substances in food for e.g., chemical contaminants (European Commission, 2023a) or residues of pharmacologically active substances (European Commission, 2023b). In addition, substances used in industry are registered under REACH (registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals), with the aim to evaluate potential impacts on human health and the environment. As for other compartments such as chemicals used in food packaging, these are registered under the EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), providing scientific advice and information about risks from chemicals present in the food chain.

The regulatory frameworks may affect a specific part or the whole life cycle of a chemical. There is a large variation in the number of chemicals that are regulated per framework, from a few to a couple of thousands. Whereas chemicals such as plant protection products or biocides are authorised in the EU, industrial chemicals under REACH are marketed directly after registration. The fragmented approach of chemical regulations has resulted in heterogeneous data requirements and frequently non-compliant registration dossiers under REACH. In most cases concerning potential exposure from chemicals to humans or an ecosystem, regulatory frameworks will only cover a very small part of the total number of

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 26

individual chemicals, and not consider mixture toxicity effects. The risks that arise from unregulated CECs entail and require a continuous review of the different directives.

The EWS proposed herein, incorporating chemical screening techniques such as wide-scope, suspect and non-targeted screening and EBM, will include a more complete evaluation of factors linked with ecological and chemical status and enable a larger set of chemicals to be covered. In this way, chemical and effect-based screening should provide a more robust chemical monitoring including exposure and effect assessment.

A low number of chemicals in current framework directives and an absence of a holistic assessment for ecological and human health depend on an analysis and judgement of the actual contamination of the chemicals. Recently, van Gils et al. (2019) discussed how monitoring could be improved by model trains involving field data and gathered information on chemical risk drivers. They demonstrated how models can successfully link present gaps between monitoring sites and the identification of areas at risk. To estimate when risks prevail, EBT values for a variety of bioassays have been defined and applied in water sources to assess risks from complex mixtures by taking advantage of already defined environmental quality standards (EQS) (B. Escher et al., 2018; Robitaille et al., 2022). As B.I. Escher et al. (2018) points out, the EBTs for e.g., estrogenicity could be implemented in the EU regulation. Currently, in analogy to using *in vitro* bioassays for environmental monitoring, EBTs are being derived in the EU funded project Panoramix (<https://panoramix-h2020.eu>), to explore the applicability of these effect-based methods for human biomonitoring, in combination with EDA and suspect and nontarget screening.

Under the CIS (Common implementation strategy) of the WFD an activity, in which several MA have participated, on EBM has been performed and 2 technical reports have been published (Wernersson et al., 2015; EC 2021)

In the second 2021 technical report it is clearly mentioned that the use of EBMs under the legislative framework could act as early warning of effects before adverse outcomes at population level occur (precautionary principle); this point is particularly relevant to the effects of climate change (e.g. through flooding) on chemical contamination,

In 2022 the European Commission published a new proposal directive (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-amending-water-directives_en)

in relation to the chemical status of the WFD. In this proposal there is a new concept of environmental quality standard in which EBM (Effect-Based Methods) are included: 'Environmental quality standard means the concentration of a particular pollutant or group of pollutants in water, sediment or biota not to be exceeded in order to protect human health and the environment or a trigger value for the adverse effect on human health or the environment of such a pollutant or group of pollutants measured using an appropriate EBM'. Furthermore, it is foreseen that Member States, for a period of two years, monitor the

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 27

presence of estrogenic substances in water bodies, using effect-based monitoring methods. They shall conduct the monitoring at least four times during each of the two years at locations where the three estrogenic hormones 7-beta estradiol (E2), estrone (E1) and alpha-ethinyl estradiol (EE2) listed, are being monitored using conventional analytical methods.

3.1.2.2 Harmonization of regulatory frameworks

One of the key elements that have been raised to improve the management of chemicals in the EU is the need for a harmonization of regulations (Hale et al., 2022; Munthe et al., 2019). The current regulatory landscape is fragmented with different regulations covering the same chemical, and many chemicals that may be problematic are not presently covered by any regulation. There are also many exemptions, for example pharmaceuticals, and polymers. The concept of “one compound – one assessment” has long been a target for improvement of chemical regulation. An inventory of databases of chemical regulation and corresponding chemicals have been produced both in the Solutions project¹ as well as by ECHA².

The introduction of the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment (COM/2020/667) is a big step towards an improvement in the management of chemical risks for both the environment and human health, even though there is a significant focus on the implementation of upstream measures which may not have an immediate effect on the current status of environmental compartments. The toxic free hierarchy nevertheless requires the promotion of safe and sustainable chemicals to prevent harm to humans and the environment, minimizing environmental and human exposure to hazardous substances through risk management and better information to users. It also requires elimination of substances of concern in waste and raw materials as far as possible and the restoration of human health and the environment to a good quality status. Actions aimed at reducing the chemical pollution in the natural environment are:

- Revision of the CLP (classification, labelling and packaging) regulation and the REACH regulations
- Introduction of endocrine disrupting, PMT (persistent, mobile and toxic) and vPvM (very persistent and very mobile) compounds as categories of substances of very high concern (SVHC)
- eEnsuring a better availability of information for environmental risk assessment
- Addressing the impact of pharmaceuticals on the environment,
- A specific target on PFAS also aims at reducing the risk from this large group of compounds.

¹ <https://apps.ivl.se/Solutions/>.

² <https://echa.europa.eu/sv/legislation-finder>.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 28

The chemicals strategy also strives at simplification of the regulatory frameworks for chemicals. It specifically aims for a “one substance, one assessment” approach, making the assessment process simpler and more transparent. It will ensure that the safety assessments are being performed in a coordinated, transparent, and harmonised manner considering specific requirements of different sectors. Optimizing the use of available resources and working with groups of chemicals is necessary for efficient risk evaluation of chemicals. Providing good access to data, including sharing and reuse, and making sure that methodologies are made more coherent and, if possible, harmonized is further stressed. The high ambitions of the chemicals strategy are necessary for the long term goals of a toxic free environment in EU.

3.1.2.3 Regulatory frameworks and non-regulated compounds

Significant progress has been made in recent years concerning the possibilities of using chemical screening methods and effect-based methods to aid the management of different environmental compartments, but there is still a need for development before these techniques can be fully utilized. Hollender et al. (2019) discussed that HRMS based techniques may provide useful data. Whereas such methodologies were already frequently used for the status assessment in European Environmental Legislation Framework such as the WFD (see JDS4, (Ng et al., 2023) or the MSFD ([HELCOM](#), OSPAR, EMBLAS), there is no routine consideration of monitoring data under European Chemical Legislation. Currently, such data can only be considered in a weight-of-evidence approach during the registration (e.g. to draw conclusions on hazard endpoints or during SVHC identification under the REACH regulation (Treu et al., 2022). Furthermore, there is no renewal of registration dossiers under REACH, whereas registration dossiers for plant protection products and biocides are only renewed every 10 years (van Dijk et al., 2021)

Therefore, the information in registration dossiers does not necessarily reflect the latest scientific findings. There is clearly the need for a strategy to consider monitoring data and additional findings on hazard endpoints on a routine basis during European Chemical legislations.

Brack et al. (2019) provide suggestions for the implementation of a battery of *in-vitro*- and *in-vivo* tests to support the management of European waters and overcome identified pitfalls with regard to cumulative effects otherwise overlooked in the present workflow of the WFD (Posthuma et al., 2019; van Wezel et al., 2017). Suggested guidelines for the use of the results of *in-vitro* tests in water management have been published in the Joint NORMAN and Water Europe Position Paper (2019) and projects have recently been performed where suspect and nontarget screening and effect-based methods have been used in combination, also pointing to the recommendations on actions due to exceedance of EBT values. Chemical screening techniques, especially if they provide quantitative or semi quantitative data of identified

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 29

substances, are key to measuring the large range of chemicals that could be responsible for a significant contribution to a measured effect from an effect-based method.

The management of different environmental compartments based on semi quantitative or qualitative data, including tentatively assigned chemical identities and effect-based method data, still requires further development. For water bodies that are impacted by a wide range of non-regulated chemicals that may cause a decrease in the environmental status, the precautionary principle may be feasible to use for the implementation of measures with the Weser ruling (C-461/13) as a precedent. A mechanism for implementation of short-term and long-term measures, based on the results of NTS, effect-based method (*in vitro* tests) and modelling is required for the effective implementation of an EWS.

3.1.2.4 The regulatory cycle

The management of water bodies by water authorities is performed in six-year cycles (Water Framework Directive, 2000/60/EC). Improving the environmental status in a specific body of water, or the risk of exposure to a chemical mixture or to mixtures of priority contaminants and CECs over the course of one cycle based on the results from NTS, EBM and modelling would require continuous chemical and effect-based status evaluation. There is also a need for guidance on how to interpret results from these techniques and how they can be used to assess an improvement in the environmental status of a specific environmental compartment. Harmonized protocols for chemical analysis and quality requirements, infrastructure for data management, evaluation and data sharing, are further needed to facilitate comparisons over time and geographically in order to determine the presence and trends of specific chemical signals.

3.2 Computational integration

Computational integration aims at the development of the functional environment that involves the best suited tools, based on the availability of data that eventually trigger (Step 1 of the methodology) or amplify (Step 3) an early warning signal. This is critical in order to continuously adapt the workflows on the emerging needs of the EWS as well as for the integration of additional tools that might become available in the course of the PARC project from the various WPs. Equally important is to ensure link with databases for data that relate to various aspects of chemical safety and sustainability such as chemical structures, tonnage, physicochemical properties, toxicity, ancillary exposure data, carbon footprint and other sustainability indexes. Databases in this direction include the ECHA CLP C&L Inventory, PubChem, eChemportal, ECOTOX, RISCTOX, NORMAN, CompTox Chemicals Dashboard, CAMEO Chemicals, Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (CheBI), ChemSpider, ChemView, OpenFoodTox, ChEMBL, and OSHA Occupational Chemical Database. Models for safety aspects include INTEGRA, OECD SAAToolbox, ConsExpo, OECD QSAR Toolbox, QSARs lab

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 30

database, VEGAHUB, GreenScreen for Safer Chemicals, AMBIT tool and ECETOC TRA. Finally, FAIRification of both the models and the workflow will be done, in order to ensure broad regulatory acceptance.

A central interface that will form/describe the pipeline of the EWS will be created. The user interface will be web-based; in some cases (for specific tools) they may be a client-side application, executed from the web browser's window that will guide the user through the PARC EWS computational platform.

For authentication and authorization, we will strive for all PARC systems to have a single-sign-on (SSO). To this end, we consider Life Science Login (formerly ELIXIR AAI) as the most viable solution.

Details on the computational implementation of the PARC EWS are presented in AD8.3 "Conceptualization of a computational system using AI and systems modeling for environmental and human samples and products for the EWS".

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 31

4 References

- Abdullah, Jamari, A. Z., Daril, M. A. M., Wahab, M. I. A., Subari, K., & Abdullah, S. M. (2022). Sustainable IoT-Based Environmental and Industrial Monitoring System. In *Advanced Transdisciplinary Engineering and Technology* (pp. 171-186). Springer.
- Ahmed, H. O., Attaelmanan, A. G., AlShaer, F. I., & Abdallah, E. M. (2021). Determination of metals in children's plastic toys using X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int*, 28(32), 43970-43984. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-13838-1>
- Alygizakis, N., Gago-Ferrero, P., Hollender, J., & Thomaidis, N. S. (2019). Untargeted time-pattern analysis of LC-HRMS data to detect spills and compounds with high fluctuation in influent wastewater. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 361, 19-29.
- Alygizakis, N., Giannakopoulos, T., Thomaidis, N. S., & Slobodnik, J. (2022). Detecting the sources of chemicals in the Black Sea using non-target screening and deep learning convolutional neural networks. *Science of the Total Environment*, 847, 157554.
- Alygizakis, N., Ng, K., Maragou, N., Alirai, S., Behnisch, P., Besselink, H., Oswald, P., Čirka, L., Thomaidis, N. S., & Slobodnik, J. (2023). Battery of In Vitro Bioassays: A Case Study for the Cost-Effective and Effect-Based Evaluation of Wastewater Effluent Quality. *Water*, 15(4), 619.
- Alygizakis, N. A., Samanipour, S., Hollender, J., Ibáñez, M., Kaserzon, S., Kokkali, V., van Leerdam, J. A., Mueller, J. F., Pijnappels, M., Reid, M. J., Schymanski, E. L., Slobodnik, J., Thomaidis, N. S., & Thomas, K. V. (2018). Exploring the Potential of a Global Emerging Contaminant Early Warning Network through the Use of Retrospective Suspect Screening with High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry. *Environ Sci Technol*, 52(9), 5135-5144. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b00365>
- AMAP assessment report. (1998). *AMAP assessment report: Arctic pollution issues*. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP).
- Anderson, H. R., Limb, E. S., Bland, J. M., De Leon, A. P., Strachan, D. P., & Bower, J. S. (1995). Health effects of an air pollution episode in London, December 1991. *Thorax*, 50(11), 1188-1193.
- Ardisasmita, A. I., Schene, I. F., Joore, I. P., Kok, G., Hendriks, D., Artegiani, B., Mokry, M., Nieuwenhuis, E. E. S., & Fuchs, S. A. (2022). A comprehensive transcriptomic comparison of hepatocyte model systems improves selection of models for experimental use. *Communications Biology*, 5(1), 1094. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-04046-9>
- Arroyo, P., Herrero, J. L., Suárez, J. I., & Lozano, J. (2019). Wireless sensor network combined with cloud computing for air quality monitoring. *Sensors*, 19(3), 691.
- Badry, A., Slobodnik, J., Alygizakis, N., Bunke, D., Cincinelli, A., Claßen, D., Dekker, R. W. R. J., Duke, G., Dulio, V., Göckener, B., Gkotsis, G., Hanke, G., Jartun, M., Movalli, P., Nika, M.-C., Rüdell, H., Thomaidis, N. S., Tarazona, J. V., Tornero, V., . . . Koschorreck, J. (2022). Using environmental monitoring data from apex predators for chemicals management: towards harmonised sampling and processing of archived wildlife samples to increase the regulatory uptake of monitoring data in chemicals management. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 34(1), 81. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-022-00664-6>

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 32

- Baken, K. A., Sjerps, R. M. A., Schriks, M., & van Wezel, A. P. (2018). Toxicological risk assessment and prioritization of drinking water relevant contaminants of emerging concern. *Environ Int*, *118*, 293-303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.05.006>
- Bakker, J., Reihlen, A., Meura, L., Camboni, M., Goldenman, G., & Lietzmann, J. (2017). *Study for the strategy for a non-toxic environment of the 7th Environment Action Programme : final report*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/doi/10.2779/025>
- Bell, M. L., & Davis, D. L. (2001). Reassessment of the lethal London fog of 1952: novel indicators of acute and chronic consequences of acute exposure to air pollution. *Environmental health perspectives*, *109*(suppl 3), 389-394.
- Berglund, J. (2015). Utvärdering av ny utrustning för modalprovning. In.
- Berthiller, F., Werner, U., Sulyok, M., Krska, R., Hauser, M.-T., & Schuhmacher, R. (2006). Liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) determination of phase II metabolites of the mycotoxin zearalenone in the model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Food Additives and Contaminants*, *23*(11), 1194-1200.
- Blümmel, T., Rehn, J., Mereu, C., Graf, F., Kneuer, C., Wittkowski, P., Sonnenburg, A., Moore, A., Bech, K., van der Lugt, B., Bouwmeester, H., Kramer, N., & Dobrikov, T. (2023). Review of state-of-the-art AI tools and methods for screening, extracting and evaluating NAMs literature in the context of chemical risk assessment [<https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7815>]. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, *20*(1), 7815E. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7815>
- Bocca, B., Pino, A., Alimonti, A., & Forte, G. (2014). Toxic metals contained in cosmetics: A status report. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, *68*(3), 447-467. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2014.02.003>
- Bocca, B., Ruggieri, F., Pino, A., Rovira, J., Calamandrei, G., Martínez, M., Domingo, J. L., Alimonti, A., & Schuhmacher, M. (2019). Human biomonitoring to evaluate exposure to toxic and essential trace elements during pregnancy. Part A. concentrations in maternal blood, urine and cord blood. *Environ Res*, *177*, 108599. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108599>
- Boulard, L., Dierkes, G., Schlüsener, M. P., Wick, A., Koschorreck, J., & Ternes, T. A. (2020). Spatial distribution and temporal trends of pharmaceuticals sorbed to suspended particulate matter of German rivers. *Water Research*, *171*, 115366. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2019.115366>
- Boulard, L., Parrhysius, P., Jacobs, B., Dierkes, G., Wick, A., Buchmeier, G., Koschorreck, J., & Ternes, T. A. (2020). Development of an analytical method to quantify pharmaceuticals in fish tissues by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry detection and application to environmental samples. *Journal of Chromatography A*, *1633*, 461612. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2020.461612>
- Bouzembrak, Y., & Marvin, H. J. (2016). Prediction of food fraud type using data from Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) and Bayesian network modelling. *Food Control*, *61*, 180-187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2015.09.026>
- Bouzembrak, Y., Steen, B., Neslo, R., Linge, J., Mojtahed, V., & Marvin, H. (2018). Development of food fraud media monitoring system based on text mining. *Food Control*, *93*, 283-296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2018.06.003>
- Brack, W. (2003). Effect-directed analysis: a promising tool for the identification of organic toxicants in complex mixtures? *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, *377*, 397-407.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 33

- Brack, W., Aissa, S. A., Backhaus, T., Dulio, V., Escher, B. I., Faust, M., Hilscherova, K., Hollender, J., Hollert, H., Müller, C., Munthe, J., Posthuma, L., Seiler, T.-B., Slobodnik, J., Teodorovic, I., Tindall, A. J., de Aragão Umbuzeiro, G., Zhang, X., & Altenburger, R. (2019). Effect-based methods are key. The European Collaborative Project SOLUTIONS recommends integrating effect-based methods for diagnosis and monitoring of water quality. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-019-0192-2>
- Brack, W., Ait-Aissa, S., Burgess, R. M., Busch, W., Creusot, N., Di Paolo, C., Escher, B. I., Hewitt, L. M., Hilscherova, K., & Hollender, J. (2016). Effect-directed analysis supporting monitoring of aquatic environments—an in-depth overview. *Science of the Total Environment*, 544, 1073-1118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.11.102>
- Bruks, S., Andersson, P., F., V., & Wiberg, K. (2021). Methods for early identification of chemicals that have the potential to harm human health or the environment. *Toxicological Council of Sweden Research report*, 1-45.
- Brunner, A. M., Dingemans, M. M., Baken, K. A., & van Wezel, A. P. (2019). Prioritizing anthropogenic chemicals in drinking water and sources through combined use of mass spectrometry and ToxCast toxicity data. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 364, 332-338.
- Cacciamali, A., Villa, R., & Dotti, S. (2022). 3D Cell Cultures: Evolution of an Ancient Tool for New Applications [Review]. 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2022.836480>
- Cartwright, N., Martin, I., Massey, C., Newman, J., Sims, K., & Wilkinson, H. (2021). *Prioritisation and Early Warning System for Chemicals of Emerging Concern -a year of evolution of the Environment Agency's approach*.
- Cerna, M., Krskova, A., Cejchanova, M., & Spevackova, V. (2012). Human biomonitoring in the Czech Republic: an overview. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*, 215(2), 109-119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2011.09.007>
- Chakraborty, C., Sharma, A. R., Sharma, G., & Lee, S.-S. (2016). Zebrafish: A complete animal model to enumerate the nanoparticle toxicity. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, 14(1), 65. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-016-0217-6>
- Chapman, S. W., & Parker, B. L. (2005). Plume persistence due to aquitard back diffusion following dense nonaqueous phase liquid source removal or isolation. 41(12). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1029/2005WR004224>
- Choi, P. M., Tschärke, B. J., Donner, E., O'Brien, J. W., Grant, S. C., Kaserzon, S. L., Mackie, R., O'Malley, E., Crosbie, N. D., Thomas, K. V., & Mueller, J. F. (2018). Wastewater-based epidemiology biomarkers: Past, present and future. *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 105, 453-469. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2018.06.004>
- Corsolini, S., Covaci, A., Ademollo, N., Focardi, S., & Schepens, P. (2006). Occurrence of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) and their enantiomeric signatures, and concentrations of polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) in the Adélie penguin food web, Antarctica. *Environmental Pollution*, 140(2), 371-382.
- Cuykx, M., Beirnaert, C., Rodrigues, R. M., Laukens, K., Vanhaecke, T., & Covaci, A. (2019). Exposure of HepaRG Cells to Sodium Saccharin Underpins the Importance of Including Non-Hepatotoxic Compounds When Investigating Toxicological Modes of Action Using Metabolomics. *Metabolites*, 9(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo9110265>

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 34

- Dent, M., Amaral, R. T., Da Silva, P. A., Ansell, J., Boisleve, F., Hatao, M., Hirose, A., Kasai, Y., Kern, P., & Kreiling, R. J. C. T. (2018). Principles underpinning the use of new methodologies in the risk assessment of cosmetic ingredients. *7*, 20-26.
- Dereumeaux, C., Fillol, C., Charles, M. A., & Denys, S. (2017). The French human biomonitoring program: First lessons from the perinatal component and future needs. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*, *220*(2 Pt A), 64-70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2016.11.005>
- Dodson, R. E., Camann, D. E., Morello-Frosch, R., Brody, J. G., & Rudel, R. A. (2015). Semivolatile organic compounds in homes: strategies for efficient and systematic exposure measurement based on empirical and theoretical factors. *Environ Sci Technol*, *49*(1), 113-122. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es502988r>
- EEA. (2001). Late lessons from early warnings: the precautionary principle 1896–2000.
- EEA. (2013). Late lessons from early warnings: science, precaution, innovation. *European Environment Agency*.
- EFSA. (2007). Definition and Description of “Emerging Risks” within the EFSA’S Mandate. *European Food Safety Authority*
- EFSA. (2014b). Further development and update of EFSA's Chemical Hazards Database (NP/EFSA/EMRISK/2012/01). *11*(9), 654E. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2014.EN-654>
- EFSA. (2021). TERMS OF REFERENCE OF THE EFSA EMERGING RISKS EXCHANGE NETWORK (EREN) – 3rd update.
- EFSA, E. F. S. A. (2014a). A systematic procedure for the identification of emerging chemical risks in the food and feed chain. *11*(1), 547E. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2014.EN-547>
- EIONET. (2023). *European Environment Information and Observation Network*. <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/>
- EMEP. (2023). *CCC reports*. <https://projects.nilu.no/ccc/reports.html>
- Entzeroth, M., Flotow, H., & Condron, P. (2009). Overview of high-throughput screening. *Curr Protoc Pharmacol*, *Chapter* 9, *Unit* 9.4. <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471141755.ph0904s44>
- Escher, B., Neale, P., & Leusch, F. (2018). Bioanalytical Tools in Water Quality Assessment. *IWA publishing*, 294.
- Escher, B. I., Aït-Aïssa, S., Behnisch, P. A., Brack, W., Brion, F., Brouwer, A., Buchinger, S., Crawford, S. E., Du Pasquier, D., & Hamers, T. (2018). Effect-based trigger values for in vitro and in vivo bioassays performed on surface water extracts supporting the environmental quality standards (EQS) of the European Water Framework Directive. *Science of the Total Environment*, *628*, 748-765.
- Escher, B. I., Aït-Aïssa, S., Behnisch, P. A., Brack, W., Brion, F., Brouwer, A., Buchinger, S., Crawford, S. E., Du Pasquier, D., Hamers, T., Hettwer, K., Hilscherová, K., Hollert, H., Kase, R., Kienle, C., Tindall, A. J., Tuerk, J., van der Oost, R., Vermeirssen, E., & Neale, P. A. (2018). Effect-based trigger values for in vitro and in vivo bioassays performed on surface water extracts supporting the environmental quality standards (EQS) of the European Water Framework Directive. *Science of the Total Environment*, *628-629*, 748-765.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 35

- Esteban, M., & Castaño, A. (2009). Non-invasive matrices in human biomonitoring: A review. *Environment International*, 35(2), 438-449. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2008.09.003>
- EU. (2021). *Pilot of an EU early warning system for emerging chemical risks to the environment* (under Contract No. 070203/2019/820480/SER/ENV.B2070203/2019/820480/SER/ENV.B2, Issue. European Commission. (2023). *IPCHEM - the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring*. <https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>
- European Commission, Environment, D.-G. f., Bakker, J., Reihlen, A., Meura, L., Camboni, M., Goldenman, G., & Lietzmann, J. (2017). *Study for the strategy for a non-toxic environment of the 7th Environment Action Programme : final report*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/doi/10.2779/025>
- EUROSTAT. (2020). An Early-warning System (EWS) for the correct and consistent statistical treatment of restructuring events of multinational enterprise groups and their enterprises in European statistics. *European Commission Eurostat*.
- Falk, S., Stahl, T., Fliedner, A., Rüdell, H., Tarricone, K., Brunn, H., & Koschorreck, J. (2019). Levels, accumulation patterns and retrospective trends of perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) in terrestrial ecosystems over the last three decades. *Environmental Pollution*, 246, 921-931. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.12.095>
- Famele, M., Ferranti, C., Abenavoli, C., Palleschi, L., Mancinelli, R., & Draisci, R. (2015). The chemical components of electronic cigarette cartridges and refill fluids: review of analytical methods. *Nicotine & Tobacco Research*, 17(3), 271-279.
- Finch, L., Hillyer, M., & Leopold, M. (2015). Quantitative Analysis of Heavy Metals in Children's Toys and Jewelry: A Multi-Instrument, Multitechnique Exercise in Analytical Chemistry and Public Health. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 92, 849-854. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ed500647w>
- Fliedner, A., Rüdell, H., Göckener, B., Krehenwinkel, H., Paulus, M., & Koschorreck, J. (2022). Environmental specimen banks and the European Green Deal. *Science of the Total Environment*, 852, 158430. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158430>
- Freeling, F., Scheurer, M., Koschorreck, J., Hoffmann, G., Ternes, T. A., & Nödler, K. (2022). Levels and Temporal Trends of Trifluoroacetate (TFA) in Archived Plants: Evidence for Increasing Emissions of Gaseous TFA Precursors over the Last Decades. *Environmental Science & Technology Letters*, 9(5), 400-405. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.estlett.2c00164>
- Gago-Ferrero, P., Schymanski, E. L., Bletsou, A. A., Aalizadeh, R., Hollender, J., & Thomaidis, N. S. (2015). Extended suspect and non-target strategies to characterize emerging polar organic contaminants in raw wastewater with LC-HRMS/MS. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 49(20), 12333-12341.
- García, L., Garcia-Sanchez, A.-J., Asorey-Cacheda, R., Garcia-Haro, J., & Zúñiga-Cañón, C.-L. (2022). Smart Air Quality Monitoring IoT-Based Infrastructure for Industrial Environments. *Sensors*, 22(23), 9221.
- Gavai, A. K., Bouzembrak, Y., van den Bulk, L. M., Liu, N., van Overbeeke, L. F., van den Heuvel, L. J., Mol, H., & Marvin, H. J. (2021). Artificial intelligence to detect unknown stimulants

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 36

- from scientific literature and media reports. *Food Control*, 130, 108360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2021.108360>
- Gawlik-Kobylińska, M., Gudzbeler, G., Szklarski, Ł., Kopp, N., Koch-Eschweiler, H., & Urban, M. (2021). The EU-SENSE system for chemical hazards detection, identification, and monitoring. *Applied Sciences*, 11(21), 10308. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112110308>
- Geng, Z., Zhao, S., Tao, G., & Han, Y. J. F. C. (2017). Early warning modeling and analysis based on analytic hierarchy process integrated extreme learning machine (AHP-ELM): Application to food safety. 78, 33-42.
- Gilles, L., Govarts, E., Rambaud, L., Vogel, N., Castano, A., Esteban Lopez, M., Rodriguez Martin, L., Koppen, G., Remy, S., Vrijheid, M., Montazeri, P., Birks, L., Sepai, O., Stewart, L., Fiddicke, U., Loots, I., Knudsen, L. E., Kolossa-Gehring, M., & Schoeters, G. (2021). HBM4EU combines and harmonises human biomonitoring data across the EU, building on existing capacity - The HBM4EU survey. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*, 237, 113809. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113809>
- Gilles, L., Govarts, E., Rodriguez Martin, L., Andersson, A. M., Appenzeller, B. M. R., Barbone, F., Castano, A., Coertjens, D., Den Hond, E., Dzhedzheia, V., Erzen, I., Lopez, M. E., Fabelova, L., Fillol, C., Franken, C., Frederiksen, H., Gabriel, C., Haug, L. S., Horvat, M., . . . Schoeters, G. (2022). Harmonization of Human Biomonitoring Studies in Europe: Characteristics of the HBM4EU-Aligned Studies Participants. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 19(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19116787>
- Göckener, B., Fliedner, A., Rüdell, H., Badry, A., & Koschorreck, J. (2022). Long-Term Trends of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) in Suspended Particular Matter from German Rivers Using the Direct Total Oxidizable Precursor (dTOP) Assay. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 56(1), 208-217. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c04165>
- Gray, N., Halstead, M., Gonzalez-Jimenez, N., Valentin-Blasini, L., Watson, C., & Pappas, R. S. (2019). Analysis of Toxic Metals in Liquid from Electronic Cigarettes. 16(22), 4450. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/16/22/4450>
- Guan, M.-Y., Zhong, H.-N., Wang, Z.-W., Yu, W.-W., & Hu, C.-Y. (2023). Chemical contaminants from food contact materials and articles made from or containing wood and bamboo—a review. *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A*, 40(3), 434-453.
- Guelfo, J. L., & Higgins, C. P. (2013). Subsurface Transport Potential of Perfluoroalkyl Acids at Aqueous Film-Forming Foam (AFFF)-Impacted Sites. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 47(9), 4164-4171. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es3048043>
- Gwinn, W. M., Auerbach, S. S., Parham, F., Stout, M. D., Waidyanatha, S., Mutlu, E., Collins, B., Paules, R. S., Merrick, B. A., Ferguson, S., Ramaiahgari, S., Bucher, J. R., Sparrow, B., Toy, H., Gorospe, J., Machesky, N., Shah, R. R., Balik-Meisner, M. R., Mav, D., . . . DeVito, M. J. (2020). Evaluation of 5-day In Vivo Rat Liver and Kidney With High-throughput Transcriptomics for Estimating Benchmark Doses of Apical Outcomes. *Toxicol Sci*, 176(2), 343-354. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfaa081>
- Hale, S. E., Neumann, M., Schliebner, I., Schulze, J., Averbeck, F. S., Castell-Exner, C., Collard, M., Drmač, D., Hartmann, J., Hofman-Caris, R., Hollender, J., de Jonge, M., Kullick, T., Lennquist, A., Letzel, T., Nödler, K., Pawlowski, S., Reineke, N., Rorije, E., . . . Arp, H. P. H. (2022). Getting in control of persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances to protect water resources: strategies from diverse

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 37

- perspectives. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 34(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-022-00604-4>
- Hartmann, J., van Driezum, I., Ohana, D., Lynch, G., Berendsen, B., Wuijts, S., van der Hoek, J. P., & de Roda Husman, A. M. (2020). The effective design of sampling campaigns for emerging chemical and microbial contaminants in drinking water and its resources based on literature mining. *Science of the Total Environment*, 742, 140546. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.140546>
- HBM4EU. (2022). *European Human Biomonitoring Initiative*. Retrieved 12.05.2023 from <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/733032>
- Hernández, A. F., Gil, F., & Tsatsakis, A. M. (2019). Chapter 33 - Biomarkers of Chemical Mixture Toxicity. In R. C. Gupta (Ed.), *Biomarkers in Toxicology (Second Edition)* (pp. 569-585). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814655-2.00033-5>
- Hoffman, K., Hammel, S. C., Phillips, A. L., Lorenzo, A. M., Chen, A., Calafat, A. M., Ye, X., Webster, T. F., & Stapleton, H. M. (2018). Biomarkers of exposure to SVOCs in children and their demographic associations: The TESIE Study. *Environ Int*, 119, 26-36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.06.007>
- Hollender, J., van Bavel, B., Dulio, V., Farmen, E., Furtmann, K., Koschorreck, J., Kunkel, U., Krauss, M., Munthe, J., Schlabach, M., Slobodnik, J., Stroomberg, G., Ternes, T., Thomaidis, N. S., Togola, A., & Tornero, V. (2019). High resolution mass spectrometry-based non-target screening can support regulatory environmental monitoring and chemicals management. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-019-0225-x>
- <https://apps.ivl.se/Solutions/>.
- <https://echa.europa.eu/sv/legislation-finder>.
- <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/lucas>.
- <https://panoramix-h2020.eu>. <https://panoramix-h2020.eu>
- Huang, L., Sun, D.-W., Pu, H., Zhang, C., & Zhang, D. (2023). Nanocellulose-based polymeric nanozyme as bioinspired spray coating for fruit preservation. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 135, 108138.
- Hug, C., Sievers, M., Ottermanns, R., Hollert, H., Brack, W., & Krauss, M. (2015). Linking mutagenic activity to micropollutant concentrations in wastewater samples by partial least square regression and subsequent identification of variables. *Chemosphere*, 138, 176-182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.05.072>
- Hug, C., Ulrich, N., Schulze, T., Brack, W., & Krauss, M. (2014). Identification of novel micropollutants in wastewater by a combination of suspect and nontarget screening. *Environmental Pollution*, 184, 25-32.
- IPCHEM. (2018). Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring, Quick reference guide for end-users.
- Jin, C., Bouzembrak, Y., Zhou, J., Liang, Q., Van Den Bulk, L. M., Gavai, A., Liu, N., Van Den Heuvel, L. J., Hoenderdaal, W., & Marvin, H. J. (2020). Big Data in food safety-A review. *Current Opinion in Food Science*, 36, 24-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2020.11.006>
- Joint NORMAN and Water Europe Position Paper. (2019). Contaminants of Emerging Concern in Urban Wastewater *Joint NORMAN and Water Europe Position Paper*.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 38

https://www.normandata.eu/sites/default/files/files/Publications/Position%20paper%20CECs%20UWW%20NORMAN%20WE%202019%20Final%2020190910_public.pdf

- Jørgensen, L., Villholth, K., & Refsgaard, J. (2016). Groundwater management and protection in Denmark: a review of pre-conditions, advances and challenges. *International Journal of Water Resources Development*, 33, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07900627.2016.1225569>
- Joseph, P. (2017). Transcriptomics in toxicology. *Food Chem Toxicol*, 109(Pt 1), 650-662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2017.07.031>
- Kalina, J., White, K. B., Scheringer, M., Příbylová, P., Kukučka, P., Audy, O., Martiník, J., & Klánová, J. (2022). Comparability of semivolatile organic compound concentrations from co-located active and passive air monitoring networks in Europe. *Environ Sci Process Impacts*, 24(6), 898-909. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2em00007e>
- Kampouris, I. D., Alygizakis, N., Klümper, U., Agrawal, S., Lackner, S., Cacace, D., Kunze, S., Thomaidis, N. S., Slobdonik, J., & Berendonk, T. U. (2022). Elevated levels of antibiotic resistance in groundwater during treated wastewater irrigation associated with infiltration and accumulation of antibiotic residues. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 423, 127155. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.127155>
- Kasprzyk-Hordern, B., Adams, B., Adewale, I. D., Agunbiade, F. O., Akinyemi, M. I., Archer, E., Badru, F. A., Barnett, J., Bishop, I. J., Di Lorenzo, M., Estrela, P., Faraway, J., Fasona, M. J., Fayomi, S. A., Feil, E. J., Hyatt, L. J., Irewale, A. T., Kjeldsen, T., Lasisi, A. K. S., . . . Yinka-Banjo, C. O. (2022). Wastewater-based epidemiology in hazard forecasting and early-warning systems for global health risks. *Environment International*, 161, 107143. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107143>
- Kassotis, C. D., Hoffman, K., Phillips, A. L., Zhang, S., Cooper, E. M., Webster, T. F., & Stapleton, H. M. (2021). Characterization of adipogenic, PPAR γ , and TR β activities in house dust extracts and their associations with organic contaminants. *Sci Total Environ*, 758, 143707. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.143707>
- Khan, B., Ho, K. T., & Burgess, R. M. (2020). Application of Biomarker Tools Using Bivalve Models Toward the Development of Adverse Outcome Pathways for Contaminants of Emerging Concern. *Environ Toxicol Chem*, 39(8), 1472-1484. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.4757>
- Kim, F., Pablo, G.-F., Lubertus, B., Lutz, A., Karin, W., Félix, H., Agneta, O., & Johan, L. (2023). Effect-based evaluation of water quality in a system of indirect reuse of wastewater for drinking water production. *Water Research*, 242, 120147. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120147>
- Kiszla, B. M., Elmets, C. A., & Mayo, T. T. (2023). Quantitative analysis of restricted metals and metalloids in tattoo inks: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Chemosphere*, 313, 137291. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.137291>
- Kleter, G. A., & Marvin, H. J. P. (2009). Indicators of emerging hazards and risks to food safety. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 47(5), 1022-1039. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2008.07.028>
- Kluger, N. (2015). Contraindications for Tattooing. In J. Serup, N. Kluger, & W. Bäumlner (Eds.), *Tattooed Skin and Health* (Vol. 48, pp. 0). S.Karger AG. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000369189>

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 39

- Kotthoff, M., Fliedner, A., Rüdell, H., Göckener, B., Bücking, M., Biegel-Engler, A., & Koschorreck, J. (2020). Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in the German environment – Levels and patterns in different matrices. *Science of the Total Environment*, 740, 140116. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.140116>
- Kumar, A., & Jha, A. (2017). Chapter 7 - Drug Development Strategies. In A. Kumar & A. Jha (Eds.), *Anticandidal Agents* (pp. 63-71). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-811311-0.00007-7>
- Kumar, S., Deepika, D., & Kumar, V. (2022). Pharmacophore Modeling Using Machine Learning for Screening the Blood–Brain Barrier Permeation of Xenobiotics. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(20), 13471.
- Kuncoro, A., M. Mellyanawaty, Sambas, A., Maulana, D. S., & Mamat, M. (2020). Air Quality Monitoring System in the City of Tasikmalaya based on the Internet of Things (IoT). *Jour of Adv Research in Dynamical & Control Systems*, 12(2), 2473-2479.
- Lamarca, R. S., C. Luchiari, N., Bonjorno, A., Passaretti Filho, J., Cardoso, A., & Lima Gomes, P. (2019). Determination of formaldehyde in cosmetic products using gas-diffusion microextraction coupled with a smartphone reader. *Analytical Methods*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9AY00720B>
- Land, M., de Wit, C. A., Bignert, A., Cousins, I. T., Herzke, D., Johansson, J. H., & Martin, J. W. (2018). What is the effect of phasing out long-chain per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances on the concentrations of perfluoroalkyl acids and their precursors in the environment? A systematic review. *Environmental Evidence*, 7(1), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-017-0114-y>
- Lee, C., Paik, K., Yoo do, G., & Kim, J. H. (2014). Efficient method for optimal placing of water quality monitoring stations for an ungauged basin. *J Environ Manage*, 132, 24-31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.10.012>
- Leung, C. M., de Haan, P., Ronaldson-Bouchard, K., Kim, G.-A., Ko, J., Rho, H. S., Chen, Z., Habibovic, P., Jeon, N. L., Takayama, S., Shuler, M. L., Vunjak-Novakovic, G., Frey, O., Verpoorte, E., & Toh, Y.-C. (2022). A guide to the organ-on-a-chip. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers*, 2(1), 33. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-022-00118-6>
- Li, H., Gu, J., Hanif, A., Dhanasekar, A., & Carlson, K. (2019). Quantitative decision making for a groundwater monitoring and subsurface contamination early warning network. *Sci Total Environ*, 683, 498-507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.05.121>
- Lim, H.-H., & Shin, H.-S. (2017). Determination of volatile organic compounds including alcohols in refill fluids and cartridges of electronic cigarettes by headspace solid-phase micro extraction and gas chromatography–mass spectrometry. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, 409(5), 1247-1256. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-016-0049-0>
- Liu, N., Bouzemrak, Y., Van den Bulk, L. M., Gavai, A., van den Heuvel, L. J., & Marvin, H. J. (2022). Automated food safety early warning system in the dairy supply chain using machine learning. *Food Control*, 136, 108872. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2022.108872>
- Loaiciga, H. A. (1988). Groundwater Monitoring Network Design. In M. A. Celia, L. A. Ferrand, C. A. Brebbia, W. G. Gray, & G. F. Pinder (Eds.), *Developments in Water Science* (Vol. 36, pp. 371-376). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-5648\(08\)70116-3](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-5648(08)70116-3)

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 40

- Logan, W. P. (1953). Mortality in the London fog incident, 1952. *The lancet*, 261(6755), 336-338.
- Lopez-Herguedas, N., González-Gaya, B., Cano, A., Alvarez-Mora, I., Mijangos, L., Etxebarria, N., Zuloaga, O., Olivares, M., & Prieto, A. (2022). Effect-directed analysis of a hospital effluent sample using A-YES for the identification of endocrine disrupting compounds. *Science of the Total Environment*, 850, 157985. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157985>
- Malinowska, J. M., Palosaari, T., Sund, J., Carpi, D., Bouhifd, M., Weber, R. J. M., Whelan, M., & Viant, M. R. (2022). Integrating in vitro metabolomics with a 96-well high-throughput screening platform. *Metabolomics*, 18(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11306-021-01867-3>
- Martín-Pozo, L., Gómez-Regalado, M. d. C., Moscoso-Ruiz, I., & Zafra-Gómez, A. (2021). Analytical methods for the determination of endocrine disrupting chemicals in cosmetics and personal care products: A review. *Talanta*, 234, 122642. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2021.122642>
- Marvin, H. J., Hoenderdaal, W., Gavai, A. K., Mu, W., van den Bulk, L. M., Liu, N., Frasso, G., Ozen, N., Elliott, C., & Manning, L. (2022). Global media as an early warning tool for food fraud; an assessment of MedISys-FF. *Food Control*, 137, 108961. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2022.108961>
- Masoumi, F., & Kerachian, R. (2010). Optimal redesign of groundwater quality monitoring networks: a case study. *Environ Monit Assess*, 161(1), 247-257. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-008-0742-3>
- Meijer, J., Lamoree, M., Hamers, T., Antignac, J.-P., Hutinet, S., Debrauwer, L., Covaci, A., Huber, C., Krauss, M., Walker, D. I., Schymanski, E. L., Vermeulen, R., & Vlaanderen, J. (2021). An annotation database for chemicals of emerging concern in exposome research. *Environment International*, 152, 106511. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106511>
- Meng, X., Zhang, N., Sun, X., Niu, Z., Deng, Y., Xu, J., Bai, H., & Ma, Q. (2020). Suspect screening of 200 hazardous substances in plastic toys using ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography-hybrid quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1617, 460830.
- Miccoli, A., Marx-Stoelting, P., & Braeuning, A. (2022). The use of NAMs and omics data in risk assessment. *EFSA Journal*, 20(S2), e200908. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.e200908>
- Miller, T. H., Ng, K. T., Lamphiere, A., Cameron, T. C., Bury, N. R., & Barron, L. P. (2021). Multicompartment and cross-species monitoring of contaminants of emerging concern in an estuarine habitat. *Environmental Pollution*, 270, 116300. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.116300>
- Mitro, S. D., Dodson, R. E., Singla, V., Adamkiewicz, G., Elmi, A. F., Tilly, M. K., & Zota, A. R. (2016). Consumer Product Chemicals in Indoor Dust: A Quantitative Meta-analysis of U.S. Studies. *Environ Sci Technol*, 50(19), 10661-10672. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b02023>
- Moisès, D. J., & Kunguma, O. (2023). Strengthening Namibia's Flood Early Warning System through a Critical Gap Analysis. *Water*, 15(1), 524. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/15/1/524>

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 41

- Molka-Danielsen, J., Engelseth, P., & Wang, H. (2018). Large scale integration of wireless sensor network technologies for air quality monitoring at a logistics shipping base. *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, 10, 20-28.
- Moschet, C., Anumol, T., Lew, B. M., Bennett, D. H., & Young, T. M. (2018). Household Dust as a Repository of Chemical Accumulation: New Insights from a Comprehensive High-Resolution Mass Spectrometric Study. *Environ Sci Technol*, 52(5), 2878-2887. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b05767>
- Muir, D., Bossi, R., Carlsson, P., Evans, M., De Silva, A., Halsall, C., Rauert, C., Herzke, D., Hung, H., Letcher, R., Rigét, F., & Roos, A. (2019). Levels and trends of poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances in the Arctic environment – An update. *Emerging Contaminants*, 5, 240-271. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emcon.2019.06.002>
- Munthe, J., Lexén, J., Skårman, T., Posthuma, L., Brack, W., Altenburger, R., Brorström-Lundén, E., Bunke, D., Faust, M., Rahmberg, M., Sleuwaert, F., Slobodnik, J., van Gils, J., & van Wezel, A. (2019). Increase coherence, cooperation and cross-compliance of regulations on chemicals and water quality. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-019-0235-8>
- Nash, S. B. (2011). Persistent organic pollutants in Antarctica: current and future research priorities. *Journal of Environmental Monitoring*, 13(3), 497-504.
- Negev, M., Berman, T., Reicher, S., Sadeh, M., Ardi, R., & Shammai, Y. (2018). Concentrations of trace metals, phthalates, bisphenol A and flame-retardants in toys and other children's products in Israel. *Chemosphere*, 192, 217-224. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.10.132>
- Ng, K., Alygizakis, N., Nika, M. C., Galani, A., Oswald, P., Oswaldova, M., Cirka, L., Kunkel, U., Macherius, A., Sengl, M., Mariani, G., Tavazzi, S., Skejo, H., Gawlik, B. M., Thomaidis, N. S., & Slobodnik, J. (2023). Wide-scope target screening characterization of legacy and emerging contaminants in the Danube River Basin by liquid and gas chromatography coupled with high-resolution mass spectrometry. *Water Res*, 230, 119539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2022.119539>
- Niarchos, G., Ahrens, L., Kleja, D. B., Leonard, G., Forde, J., Bergman, J., Ribeli, E., Schütz, M., & Fagerlund, F. (2023). In-situ application of colloidal activated carbon for PFAS-contaminated soil and groundwater: A Swedish case study. 33(2), 101-110. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/rem.21746>
- NORMAN, n. (2016). NORMAN network of reference laboratories, research centres and related organisations for monitoring of emerging environmental substances. <http://www.norman-network.net/>.
- Palm, E. H., Chirsir, P., Krier, J., Thiessen, P. A., Zhang, J., Bolton, E. E., & Schymanski, E. L. (2023). ShinyTPs: Curating Transformation Products from Text Mining Results. *Environmental Science & Technology Letters*, 10(10), 865-871. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.estlett.3c00537>
- Palmen, N. (2015). *Early warning systems to detect new and emerging risks in Europe*.
- Palmen, N. (2016). *Early warning systems to detect new and emerging risks in Europe. RIVM Letter report 2016-0022*.
- Palmen, N., & Verbist, K. (2015). Prioritization of new and emerging chemical risks for workers and follow-up actions : Prioritering en follow-up acties voor nieuwe en toenemende arborisico's van stoffen.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 42

- Pamies, D., Leist, M., Coecke, S., Bowe, G., Allen, D. G., Gstraunthaler, G., Bal-Price, A., Pistollato, F., de Vries, R. B. M., Hogberg, H. T., Hartung, T., & Stacey, G. (2022). Guidance document on Good Cell and Tissue Culture Practice 2.0 (GCCP 2.0). *Altex*, 39, 30-70. <https://doi.org/10.14573/altex.2111011>
- Persson, L., Carney Almroth, B. M., Collins, C. D., Cornell, S., de Wit, C. A., Diamond, M. L., Fantke, P., Hassellöv, M., MacLeod, M., & Ryberg, M. W. (2022). Outside the safe operating space of the planetary boundary for novel entities. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 56(3), 1510-1521. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c04158>
- Phillips, A. L., Hammel, S. C., Hoffman, K., Lorenzo, A. M., Chen, A., Webster, T. F., & Stapleton, H. M. (2018). Children's residential exposure to organophosphate ester flame retardants and plasticizers: Investigating exposure pathways in the TESIE study. *Environ Int*, 116, 176-185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.04.013>
- Pirard, C., & Charlier, C. (2022). Urinary levels of parabens, phthalate metabolites, bisphenol A and plasticizer alternatives in a Belgian population: Time trend or impact of an awareness campaign? *Environ Res*, 214(Pt 2), 113852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.113852>
- Plassmann, M. M., Tengstrand, E., Åberg, K. M., & Benskin, J. P. (2016). Non-target time trend screening: a data reduction strategy for detecting emerging contaminants in biological samples. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, 408, 4203-4208.
- Posthuma, L., Altenburger, R., Backhaus, T., Kortenkamp, A., Müller, C., Focks, A., de Zwart, D., & Brack, W. (2019). Improved component-based methods for mixture risk assessment are key to characterize complex chemical pollution in surface waters. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-019-0246-5>
- Pourchet, M., Debrauwer, L., Klanova, J., Price, E. J., Covaci, A., Caballero-Casero, N., Oberacher, H., Lamoree, M., Damont, A., Fenaille, F., Vlaanderen, J., Meijer, J., Krauss, M., Sarigiannis, D., Barouki, R., Le Bizec, B., & Antignac, J.-P. (2020). Suspect and non-targeted screening of chemicals of emerging concern for human biomonitoring, environmental health studies and support to risk assessment: From promises to challenges and harmonisation issues. *Environment International*, 139, 105545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105545>
- Prakash, O., & Datta, B. (2013). Sequential optimal monitoring network design and iterative spatial estimation of pollutant concentration for identification of unknown groundwater pollution source locations. *Environ Monit Assess*, 185(7), 5611-5626. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-012-2971-8>
- Preetam, S., Nahak, B. K., Patra, S., Toncu, D. C., Park, S., Syväjärvi, M., Orive, G., & Tiwari, A. (2022). Emergence of microfluidics for next generation biomedical devices. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics: X*, 100106.
- Ram, R. N., Gadaleta, D., & Allen, T. E. H. (2022). The role of 'big data' and 'in silico' New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) in ending animal use – A commentary on progress. *Computational Toxicology*, 23, 100232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comtox.2022.100232>
- Ramirez, T., Daneshian, M., Kamp, H., Bois, F. Y., Clench, M. R., Coen, M., Donley, B., Fischer, S. M., Ekman, D. R., Fabian, E., Guillou, C., Heuer, J., Hogberg, H. T., Jungnickel, H., Keun, H. C., Krennrich, G., Krupp, E., Luch, A., Noor, F., . . . Leist, M. (2013).

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 43

- Metabolomics in toxicology and preclinical research. *Altex*, 30(2), 209-225. <https://doi.org/10.14573/altex.2013.2.209>
- RASFF, T. E. P. A. T. C. O. T. E. U. (2022). Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety.
- Rebeiro-Hargrave, A., Motlagh, N. H., Varjonen, S., Lagerspetz, E., Nurmi, P., & Tarkoma, S. (2020). MegaSense: Cyber-physical system for real-time urban air quality monitoring. 2020 15th IEEE conference on industrial electronics and applications (ICIEA),
- Richardson, B. J., Lam, P. K., & Martin, M. (2005). Emerging chemicals of concern: pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs) in Asia, with particular reference to Southern China. *Mar Pollut Bull*, 50(9), 913-920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2005.06.034>
- Rigét, F., Bignert, A., Braune, B., Dam, M., Dietz, R., Evans, M., Green, N., Gunnlaugsdóttir, H., Hoydal, K. S., & Kucklick, J. (2019). Temporal trends of persistent organic pollutants in Arctic marine and freshwater biota. *Science of the Total Environment*, 649, 99-110.
- Rigét, F., Vorkamp, K., Bossi, R., Sonne, C., Letcher, R., & Dietz, R. (2016). Twenty years of monitoring of persistent organic pollutants in Greenland biota. A review. *Environmental Pollution*, 217, 114-123.
- Robitaille, J., Denslow, N. D., Escher, B. I., Kurita-Oyamada, H. G., Marlatt, V., Martyniuk, C. J., Navarro-Martin, L., Prosser, R., Sanderson, T., Yargeau, V., & Langlois, V. S. (2022). Towards regulation of Endocrine Disrupting chemicals (EDCs) in water resources using bioassays - A guide to developing a testing strategy. *Environ Res*, 205, 112483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.112483>
- Rocha, B. A., de Oliveira, A. R. M., & Barbosa, F. (2018). A fast and simple air-assisted liquid-liquid microextraction procedure for the simultaneous determination of bisphenols, parabens, benzophenones, triclosan, and triclocarban in human urine by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *Talanta*, 183, 94-101. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2018.02.052>
- Rovira, J., Nadal, M., Schuhmacher, M., & Domingo, J. L. (2015). Human exposure to trace elements through the skin by direct contact with clothing: Risk assessment. *Environmental research*, 140, 308-316. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2015.03.032>
- Ruff, M., Mueller, M. S., Loos, M., & Singer, H. P. (2015). Quantitative target and systematic non-target analysis of polar organic micro-pollutants along the river Rhine using high-resolution mass-spectrometry – Identification of unknown sources and compounds. *Water Research*, 87, 145-154. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2015.09.017>
- Samaras, V. G., Giri, A., Zelinkova, Z., Karasek, L., Buttinger, G., & Wenzl, T. (2016). Analytical method for the trace determination of esterified 3- and 2-monochloropropanediol and glycidyl fatty acid esters in various food matrices. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1466, 136-147. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2016.08.071>
- Schindler, B. K., Esteban, M., Koch, H. M., Castano, A., Koslitz, S., Canas, A., Casteleyn, L., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Schwedler, G., Schoeters, G., Hond, E. D., Sepai, O., Exley, K., Bloemen, L., Horvat, M., Knudsen, L. E., Joas, A., Joas, R., Biot, P., . . . Angerer, J. (2014).

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 44

- The European COPHES/DEMOCOPHES project: towards transnational comparability and reliability of human biomonitoring results. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*, 217(6), 653-661. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2013.12.002>
- Schoeters, G., Govarts, E., Bruckers, L., Den Hond, E., Nelen, V., De Henauw, S., Sioen, I., Nawrot, T. S., Plusquin, M., Vriens, A., Covaci, A., Loots, I., Morrens, B., Coertjens, D., Van Larebeke, N., De Craemer, S., Croes, K., Lambrechts, N., Colles, A., & Baeyens, W. (2017). Three cycles of human biomonitoring in Flanders - Time trends observed in the Flemish Environment and Health Study. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*, 220(2 Pt A), 36-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2016.11.006>
- Schulz, C., Conrad, A., Becker, K., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Seiwert, M., & Seifert, B. (2007). Twenty years of the German Environmental Survey (GerES): human biomonitoring--temporal and spatial (West Germany/East Germany) differences in population exposure. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*, 210(3-4), 271-297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2007.01.034>
- Shin, H. M., Moschet, C., Young, T. M., & Bennett, D. H. (2020). Measured concentrations of consumer product chemicals in California house dust: Implications for sources, exposure, and toxicity potential. *Indoor Air*, 30(1), 60-75. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ina.12607>
- Stajniko, A., Snoj Tratnik, J., Kosjek, T., Mazej, D., Jagodic, M., Erzen, I., & Horvat, M. (2020). Seasonal glyphosate and AMPA levels in urine of children and adolescents living in rural regions of Northeastern Slovenia. *Environ Int*, 143, 105985. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105985>
- Strynar, M., Dagnino, S., McMahan, R., Liang, S., Lindstrom, A., Andersen, E., McMillan, L., Thurman, M., Ferrer, I., & Ball, C. (2015). Identification of novel perfluoroalkyl ether carboxylic acids (PFECAs) and sulfonic acids (PFESAs) in natural waters using accurate mass time-of-flight mass spectrometry (TOFMS). *Environmental Science & Technology*, 49(19), 11622-11630.
- Stucki, A. O., Barton-Maclaren, T. S., Bhuller, Y., Henriquez, J. E., Henry, T. R., Hirn, C., Miller-Holt, J., Nagy, E. G., Perron, M. M., Ratzlaff, D. E., Stedeford, T. J., & Clippinger, A. J. (2022). Use of new approach methodologies (NAMs) to meet regulatory requirements for the assessment of industrial chemicals and pesticides for effects on human health [Review]. 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ftox.2022.964553>
- Sturla, S. J., Boobis, A. R., FitzGerald, R. E., Hoeng, J., Kavlock, R. J., Schirmer, K., Whelan, M., Wilks, M. F., & Peitsch, M. C. (2014). Systems toxicology: from basic research to risk assessment. *Chem Res Toxicol*, 27(3), 314-329. <https://doi.org/10.1021/tx400410s>
- Szymański, P., Markowicz, M., & Mikiciuk-Olasik, E. (2012). Adaptation of high-throughput screening in drug discovery-toxicological screening tests. *Int J Mol Sci*, 13(1), 427-452. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms13010427>
- Tao, D., Zhang, D., Hu, R., Rundensteiner, E., & Feng, H. (2021). Crowdsourcing and machine learning approaches for extracting entities indicating potential foodborne outbreaks from social media. *Scientific reports*, 11(1), 21678. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-00766-w>
- Thompson, C. V., Firman, J. W., Goldsmith, M. R., Grulke, C. M., Tan, Y. M., Paini, A., Penson, P. E., Sayre, R. R., Webb, S., & Madden, J. C. (2021). A Systematic Review of Published Physiologically-based Kinetic Models and an Assessment of their Chemical Space

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 45

- Coverage. *Altern Lab Anim*, 49(5), 197-208.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/02611929211060264>
- Treu, G., Slobodnik, J., Alygizakis, N., Badry, A., Bunke, D., Cincinelli, A., Claßen, D., Dekker, R. W. R. J., Göckener, B., Gkotsis, G., Hanke, G., Duke, G., Jartun, M., Movalli, P., Nika, M.-C., Rüdél, H., Tarazona, J. V., Thomaidis, N. S., Tornero, V., . . . Dulio, V. (2022). Using environmental monitoring data from apex predators for chemicals management: towards better use of monitoring data from apex predators in support of prioritisation and risk assessment of chemicals in Europe. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 34(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-022-00665-5>
- UN, U. N. (2006). An assessment of capacities, gaps and opportunities toward building a comprehensive global early warning system for all natural hazards. *Global Survey of Early Warning Systems*
- UN, U. N. E. P. (2012). Early Warning Systems: A State of the Art Analysis and Future Directions.
<https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/32230>.
- van de Brug, F. J., Lucas Luijckx, N. B., Cnossen, H. J., & Houben, G. F. (2014). Early signals for emerging food safety risks: From past cases to future identification. *Food Control*, 39, 75-86. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2013.10.038>
- van Dijk, J., Gustavsson, M., Dekker, S. C., & van Wezel, A. P. (2021). Towards 'one substance - one assessment': An analysis of EU chemical registration and aquatic risk assessment frameworks. *J Environ Manage*, 280, 111692.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.111692>
- van Gils, J., Posthuma, L., Cousins, I. T., Lindim, C., de Zwart, D., Bunke, D., Kutsarova, S., Müller, C., Munthe, J., Slobodnik, J., & Brack, W. (2019). The European Collaborative Project SOLUTIONS developed models to provide diagnostic and prognostic capacity and fill data gaps for chemicals of emerging concern. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-019-0248-3>
- van Wezel, A. P., ter Laak, T. L., Fischer, A., Bäuerlein, P. S., Munthe, J., & Posthuma, L. (2017). Mitigation options for chemicals of emerging concern in surface waters; operationalising solutions-focused risk assessment. *Environmental Science: Water Research & Technology*, 3(3), 403-414. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7ew00077d>
- Vanryckeghem, F., Huysman, S., Van Langenhove, H., Vanhaecke, L., & Demeestere, K. (2019). Multi-residue quantification and screening of emerging organic micropollutants in the Belgian Part of the North Sea by use of Speedisk extraction and Q-Orbitrap HRMS. *Mar Pollut Bull*, 142, 350-360.
- Vitale, C. M., Lommen, A., Huber, C., Wagner, K., Garlito Molina, B., Nijssen, R., Price, E. J., Blokland, M., van Tricht, F., Mol, H. G. J., Krauss, M., Debrauwer, L., Pardo, O., Leon, N., Klanova, J., & Antignac, J.-P. (2022). Harmonized Quality Assurance/Quality Control Provisions for Nontargeted Measurement of Urinary Pesticide Biomarkers in the HBM4EU Multisite SPECIMEn Study. *Analytical Chemistry*, 94(22), 7833-7843.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.2c00061>
- Vorkamp, K., Bossi, R., Rigét, F. F., Skov, H., Sonne, C., & Dietz, R. (2015). Novel brominated flame retardants and dechlorane plus in Greenland air and biota. *Environmental Pollution*, 196, 284-291.
- Vorkamp, K., Carlsson, P., Corsolini, S., de Wit, C. A., Dietz, R., Gribble, M. O., Houde, M., Kalia, V., Letcher, R. J., & Morris, A. (2022). Influences of climate change on long-term time

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 46

- series of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in Arctic and Antarctic biota. *Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts*, 24(10), 1643-1660.
- Vorkamp, K., Rigét, F. F., Bossi, R., & Dietz, R. (2011). Temporal trends of hexabromocyclododecane, polybrominated diphenyl ethers and polychlorinated biphenyls in ringed seals from East Greenland. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 45(4), 1243-1249.
- Wang, X., Bouzembrak, Y., Lansink, A. O., & van der Fels - Klerx, H. (2022). Application of machine learning to the monitoring and prediction of food safety: A review. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 21(1), 416-434. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12868>
- Wang, X., Bouzembrak, Y., Marvin, H. J., Clarke, D., & Butler, F. (2022). Bayesian Networks modeling of diarrhetic shellfish poisoning in *Mytilus edulis* harvested in Bantry Bay, Ireland. *Harmful algae*, 112, 102171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2021.102171>
- Wolkoff, P., & Wilkins, C. K. (1994). Indoor VOCs From Household Floor Dust: Comparison of Headspace with Desorbed VOCs; Method for VOC Release Determination. 4(4), 248-254. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0668.1994.00005.x>
- Wong, F., Hung, H., Dryfhout-Clark, H., Aas, W., Bohlin-Nizzetto, P., Breivik, K., Mastromonaco, M. N., Lundén, E. B., Ólafsdóttir, K., & Sigurðsson, Á. (2021). Time trends of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and Chemicals of Emerging Arctic Concern (CEAC) in Arctic air from 25 years of monitoring. *Science of the Total Environment*, 775, 145109.
- World Health Organization. (2015). *Human biomonitoring: facts and figures*.
- Xiong, Y., Li, W., & Liu, T. (2020). Risk Early Warning of Food Quality Safety in Meat Processing Industry. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 17(18). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17186579>
- Yang, Z., & Wang, J. (2017). A new air quality monitoring and early warning system: Air quality assessment and air pollutant concentration prediction. *Environmental research*, 158, 105-117.
- Yuan, B., Rüdél, H., de Wit, C. A., & Koschorreck, J. (2022). Identifying emerging environmental concerns from long-chain chlorinated paraffins towards German ecosystems. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 424, 127607. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.127607>
- Ziółkowska, D., Syrotynska, I., Shyichuk, A., & Lamkiewicz, J. (2021). Determination of SLES in Personal Care Products by Colloid Titration with Light Reflection Measurements. 26(9), 2716. <https://www.mdpi.com/1420-3049/26/9/2716>

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 47

5 ANNEX I: Methodological elements to support an EWS

5.1 Monitoring tools

5.1.1 Role of monitoring tools in EWS

An EWS should be able to take stock of the various sources of information regarding signals for potential risks to chemicals. This entails to a broad array of technologies related to data that may come either from monitoring, or from modelling, although the latter, is more pertinent for signal amplification. In this sense, the multitude of information sources that include either exposure or hazard related data from monitoring or experimental methods, are graphically illustrated in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**, together with a framework that facilitates the organisation of the different data types. This results in the following data type clusters, where the state of the art technologies able to support EWS, are presented in detail in the following sub-chapters of Chapter 3.1.

Figure 3. Methodological elements to support an EWS – Sources of information for the EWS.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 48

5.1.2 Matrices for monitoring

5.1.2.1 Environmental monitoring

5.1.2.1.1 Air quality monitoring

Many countries around the world are experiencing worsening air pollution due to industrialization and urbanization and this results in climate change and adverse effects on human health. Therefore, advanced scientific air quality monitoring and EWS should be urgently developed to objectively evaluate degrees of air pollution and accurately predict pollutant concentrations (Yang & Wang, 2017).

Besides the adverse health effects caused by daily exposure to urban pollution, premature human death and morbidity are observed during and following periods of prolonged and abnormally high concentrations of one or more air pollutants. These pollution episodes are caused by poor atmospheric dispersion conditions (i.e., still air) in combination with unusually high pollutant emissions following events such as wildfires, dust/sandstorms, local traffic congestion, and construction works, as well as long-range (>1000km) trans-boundary air pollution. Notable historical examples of such episodes include those experienced in London in 1952 and 1991, and in areas of West Germany in 1985. Each claimed human lives prematurely and increased respiratory and cardiovascular morbidity was subsequently observed (Anderson et al., 1995; Bell & Davis, 2001; Logan, 1953).

In coordination with the World Health Organization, the European Committee has implemented several actions to monitor air quality levels that aim to reduce air pollution and related health risks. The European Environment Agency (EEA, <https://www.eea.europa.eu/>) gathers air pollution data from a wide range of sources and publishes this data on-line. Data based on five different air pollutants is combined to give the European Air Quality Index (AQI) that shows the quality of air throughout Europe in real time. This index allows users to understand more about the quality of the air in the areas where they live and work. Similar monitoring systems could also be applied in various environments such as industrial areas or heavily polluted road networks. Effective, low-cost, wireless, air quality monitors and sensors could be applied to provide real-time environmental monitoring that would help reduce a wide range of air pollutants, especially in cases where substantial variations in different pollutants are observed within a relatively small area.

A variety of both commercial and research monitoring systems using smart sensor systems and the Internet of Things (IoT) have been developed to gather and analyze data on outdoor air quality, and perform both monitoring and warning functions. Rebeiro-Hargrave et al. (2020) developed such a system to monitor urban air quality. Their MegaSense system can generate history graphs and pollution maps from the data gathered. The sensor devices used are portable and low-cost and can monitor concentrations of air pollutant gases (O₃, CO, NO₂) and PM_{2.5} particles. The system was tested in Helsinki and a pollution profile of the city was

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 49

created which was then presented as a tool to make policies to improve the city's air quality. (Kuncoro et al., 2020) designed an IoT-based air quality monitoring system that was tested in the city of Tasikmalaya, Indonesia. This system used MQ-7, MQ-131 and MQ-4 sensors to monitor concentrations of CO, O₃ and CH₄, respectively. Arduino microprocessors were employed to extract data from the sensors and forward them through the Internet to be visualized in real-time. Furthermore, several of the low-cost sensors were also suitable for monitoring particle concentrations and detecting trends. These types of air quality monitoring systems are usually deployed as Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), such as that presented by (Arroyo et al., 2019). In this study, data were gathered from ZigBee nodes and forwarded to a server via a gateway. Cloud computing systems stored, processed and monitored volatile organic compounds (VOCs) such as benzene, xylene, ethylbenzene and toluene, and the data were processed using a Support Vector Machine and a backpropagation learning algorithm.

Industrial environments have also been used in air quality measurement research. (Molka-Danielsen et al., 2018) studied the deployment of an air quality monitoring system in a logistics shipping base and how to process the data obtained in order to evaluate the potential impact of high CO₂ levels on workers. The authors suggested using smart closed-loop systems to detect spikes of potentially harmful polluting gases and to trigger actuators to provide more ventilation within the workplace. García et al. (2022) proposed a monitoring system that could be applied in industries that handle soil, stone, grain or other materials that produce particulate matter, as well as industries that produce high levels of NO₂, O₃, SO₂ and CO. Knowledge of real-time environmental pollution levels and when they exceed established standards in the workplace is vital. It is only then that correction interventions can be made, such as halting production processes for a period of time. Pollution alerts can be transmitted via conventional e-mail, smart phone applications and instant messaging. Another system that can detect early-stage pollution in industrial environments was developed by (Abdullah et al., 2022). This system is based on Arduino Mega and its sensors can detect temperature, humidity, light intensity, and gas. In this research, six types of sensors were applied: MQ 135 (air quality), MQ 8 (hydrogen), MQ 7 (carbon monoxide), MQ 2 (LPG gas), MQ 4 (methane), and MQ 6 (butane). The system uses IoT and data is transferred to a smart device using Blynk applications. In addition, it can also perform statistical data analysis and predict pollution trends.

European air monitoring of metals and organic substances are continuously performed through the European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme (EMEP), Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) and Toxic Organic Micro Pollutants (TOMPs) network. For most EMEP monitoring stations only regulated substances are measured, particle bound metals and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs), while for a few stations legacy organic pollutants and in some cases even some CECs are measured in the gaseous phase. The results from the EMEP programme are published in yearly reports (EMEP, 2023) . The MONET passive

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 50

sampling network, as well as European participants in the Global Atmospheric Passive Sampling (GAPS) network has been collecting data on chemicals in air samples for the last 20 years. Passive sampling is a cost efficient technique that can be used in combination with NTS for detection of CECs. Recent papers from the MONET network have compared the data to active sampling and have presented trends of chemicals over 15 years of monitoring (Kalina et al., 2022).

Environmental monitoring and EWS form the basis of all environmental protection work, not only in relation to scientific decision-making, but also to long-term development plans.

5.1.2.1.2 Water (surface and wastewater)

One major source of contaminants in the surface water are the wastewater treatment plants. Monitoring the quality of treated wastewater is essential to avoid unexpected contamination of the receiving aquatic environments. Bioassays with a wide-range of mode of actions have been proposed as a 'safety-net' for the quality of treated wastewater intended for agricultural reuse in the Danube river basin (Alygizakis et al., 2019). An action plan has already been proposed to the wastewater treatment plant operators (Alygizakis et al., 2023). The action plan offers clear advantages, such as the establishment of an EWS with high efficiency and low cost. The plant operators can perform in-house bioanalytical measurements and based on the exceedance of the effect-based trigger values (EBTs), they can take actions to improve the quality of the wastewater. The requirement for the application of such an EWS is the derivation of robust EBTs (Alygizakis et al., 2023; Beate I Escher et al., 2018). This is essential for the use of bioanalytical tools in the regulation, because large variations in proposed EBT values may result in misleading conclusions. Moreover, a set of 20 performance indicator substances have been proposed to monitor effluent quality by Water Europe, NORMAN Association and Swiss legislation. Both bioanalytical tools and monitoring performance compound has been conducted in context of the Joint Danube Survey 4 (JDS4) (Ng et al., 2023).

High throughput analytical methods such, LC-HRMS and Gas Chromatography (GC) - HRMS, can capture a very wide broad of CECs and in this sense, they can also act as an EWS. This type of EWS has been adapted in the Rhine, where countries analyse daily samples from the river basin by LC-HRMS (Ruff et al., 2015). The application of LC-HRMS or/and GC-HRMS require advanced analytical instrumentation and personnel with high expertise. However, within a single chromatographic run, the instruments can record signals of contaminants in a given sample. In the margins of the analytical conditions (e.g., sampling, enrichment method and solvents used) and instrumental limitations (e.g., ionizability, selectivity, sensitivity and resolution), the full mass spectral information of detectable compounds is stored in raw data files. This raw data can be preserved in digital archives, such as the NORMAN Digital Sample Freezing Platform, for future processing with updated spectral libraries or more advanced

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 51

software (Alygizakis et al., 2019). Numerous successful applications of digital archiving and retrospective suspect screening have been documented, with the monitoring of the Danube River basin being a notable example (Ng et al., 2023). Wastewater-Based Epidemiology (WBE) offers large-scale insights into human activity within specific areas. This method allows for evaluations at a community level regarding how much of a particular chemical or biological substance is used, exposed to, or released per person. By analyzing the presence of these substances in wastewater, it's possible to gain insights, both qualitative and quantitative, into the overall exposure of the population. This approach enables assessments of trends over time or across different areas, responding to events within these catchments. Additionally, normalizing data according to population size allows for direct comparisons between catchments of varying population sizes. Consequently, WBE displays potential as a valuable tool for an EWS, particularly in profiling non-communicable diseases and tracking the use or exposure to various chemical substances ((Choi et al., 2018; Kasprzyk-Hordern et al., 2022). Finally, molecular monitoring techniques, including the monitoring of antibiotic resistant genes (ARGs), bacteria (ARBs), and environmental DNA, can play a crucial role in EWS and track the effects of climate change. These non-traditional contaminant monitoring methods offer valuable insights into biodiversity and provide evidence of the progression, whether positive or negative, of phenomena such as antibiotic resistance. Time-trend analysis, in particular, can serve as an effective EWS (Kampouris et al., 2022).

5.1.2.1.3 Soil and groundwater

Soils can act as significant sinks of pollutants, from which chemicals can leach through seepage waters into groundwater and get transported via groundwater flow, eventually putting drinking water sources at risk. Soil contamination is therefore especially relevant in cases where drinking water relies on groundwater sources, for instance in the case of Denmark, which depends wholly on groundwater for drinking water (Jørgensen et al., 2016). Effective monitoring of soil and groundwater plays a crucial role in restricting the further spreading of contaminants and implementing mitigation strategies. The presence of chemicals in these matrices is highly dependent on their solvation properties, i.e., their solubility and partitioning behaviour. Many chemicals are persistent in the subsurface for long time periods and therefore constitute a potential risk for many years and even decades. For instance, dense non-aqueous liquids (DNAPLs) are known to cause persistent plumes in groundwater (Chapman & Parker, 2005). On the other hand, highly soluble chemicals, such as Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and several pesticides, are more prone to leaching into groundwater and can diffuse far from point sources (Guelfo & Higgins, 2013). The LUCAS project (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/lucas>) by Eurostat in EU Member States assesses soil and land dynamics. It involves collecting topsoil samples to analyse environmental factors, update soil maps, and measure organic carbon content. The survey indirectly contributes to understanding groundwater impacts from land management. The LUCAS project supports policy making in nature protection, agriculture, and climate change monitoring data, offering insights into sustainable land management.

The selection of appropriate investigation sites is a key step for strategic groundwater monitoring; these can be based on geographical criteria (e.g., proximity to point sources, population density) and

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 52

hydrogeological information (e.g., groundwater elevation, flow patterns) at a regional scale. Due to limitations on the amount of monitoring wells that can be installed, there can often be uncertainty regarding the exact location of groundwater pollution sources, as well as their exact number. Another reported challenge of groundwater monitoring is that the groundwater flow and contaminant transport can be various in time (Niarchos et al., 2023; Prakash & Datta, 2013). To overcome such issues, different methods related to the efficient selection of groundwater sampling locations have been suggested. Loaiciga (1988) proposed many years ago the methodological design of groundwater monitoring networks, which can optimise a sampling plan based on background site information, such as number of available wells and their locations, and sampling frequency. More recently, entropy theory has been utilised to assess sampling efficiency of surface water (Lee et al., 2014) and groundwater (Masoumi & Kerachian, 2010). Monitoring of groundwater quality has also been proposed as an EWS for contamination (Li et al., 2019). Specifically, Li et al. (2019) exhibited a quantitative method for the early detection of contamination related to oil and gas operations, by optimising the groundwater monitoring network based on geographical and geohydrological data.

5.1.2.1.4 House dust

Chemical levels in indoor surroundings like air, particles in the air, and dust settled on floors have been employed to define how much people are exposed to indoor pollutants at home. Household dust, seen as a collection point for chemicals coming from home materials and consumer products, commonly holds phthalates, flame retardants, pesticides, PAHs, phenols, and PFAS. These substances can exist in vastly different concentrations within dust. (Dodson et al., 2015; Mitro et al., 2016; Shin et al., 2020) Analyzing and understanding these contaminants in dust and their impact on human health is crucial for comprehensive risk assessment, making dust a very important matrix for an EWS. While the vast majority of toxicological studies assess exposures to single contaminants, we know that humans are routinely exposed to hundreds or thousands of man-made chemicals from indoor and outdoor environments (Hoffman et al., 2018; Kassotis et al., 2021; Phillips et al., 2018). Although traditional targeted analytical approaches concentrate on recognized chemical categories, advancements in HRMS offer the potential not only to identify known compounds (targets) but also expected compounds using existing databases, libraries, or software matching algorithms (suspects). Furthermore, it allows for the detection of previously unknown compounds (non-targets) through examination HRMS spectra (Moschet et al., 2018; Shin et al., 2020). Using suspect screening and non-target methods is important for thoroughly examining the chemical composition of dust and its potential health impacts, strengthening its application for EWS.

5.1.2.1.5 Monitoring time trends (across environmental compartments)

Monitoring time trends in environmental matrices can provide important information on the effectiveness of European regulations and risk mitigation measures. Many environmental specimen banks can provide trend information across environmental compartments, which allows for a comprehensive environmental assessment (Fliedner et al., 2022). However, it is

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 53

essential not only to cover various environment media but also provide long-term trends to assess shifts in e.g., chemical production and their effect on the environment. One recent example are trend analyses for PFAS in riverine SPM and fish from Germany are, which showed decreasing trends for long-chained PFAS, whereas short-chained substitutes tended to increase (Göckener et al., 2022). The example of PFAS also demonstrates the necessity of monitoring various environmental matrices as long-chained PFAS are dominantly detected in sorptive matrices such as SPM (and biota), whereas shorter-chain PFAS accumulate in water, plants and soils (Falk et al., 2019; Freeling et al., 2022; Kotthoff et al., 2020). It is also important to understand that declining trends of persistent chemicals across environmental matrices are still not necessarily associated with their environmental degradation as some chemicals might show long-range transport to remote regions such as the Arctic or Antarctic (Land et al., 2018; Muir et al., 2019). This further underlines the necessity of a holistic approach when assessing temporal trends of chemicals in the environment. For biota, the detection of chemical signals is complex due to the different species-dependent ecological characteristics. For vertebrates, particularly lipophilic compounds (Persistent organic pollutants - POPs) and proteinophilic (PFAS) substances have shown to be most relevant. However, also non-accumulative chemicals such as pharmaceuticals were frequently detected in aquatic species as a result of their high sales and limited wastewater removal (Boulard, Parrhysius, et al., 2020; Miller et al., 2021). These examples demonstrate that physicochemical properties alone are not solely responsible for the detection of chemicals in biota. Particularly the use patterns, food web and spatiotemporal exposure context are important for factors for exposure. In general, monitoring chemicals in biota has the potential to provide indications of human exposures, either via food (e.g., fish) or via similar exposure pathways (in case of predatory species).

Environmental specimen banks are important repositories for supporting the establishment of European EWS by providing standardised samples and high-quality monitoring data from various environmental compartments (Fliedner et al., 2022). Specimen banks are by default forward looking instruments that have been implemented to identify unknown or ignored environmental stressors at the time of sampling as well as to establish time trends for legacy and emerging contaminants (Fliedner et al., 2022). In many specimen banks, samples are archived from the 1980s onwards, which makes it possible to identify time trends and track changes in contamination patterns over time. For example, the German environmental specimen bank contains standardised samples from three main European rivers (SPM, Rhine, Danube, Elbe) from 2005 onwards (Göckener et al., 2022). Such samples can be used to derive long-term trends for chemicals in major chemical production regions. Furthermore, riverine trend data has shown correlations with market data for pharmaceuticals (Boulard, Dierkes, et al., 2020) and can also be used to describe general shifts in market patterns (Göckener et

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 54

al., 2022). The examples of environmental specimen bank demonstrate the necessity of a holistic approach and high-quality samples to reliably assess environmental health.

5.1.2.2 Food contaminants

Main food contaminants to be identified / and the analytical techniques A 'contaminant' is defined in legislation (Regulation (EEC) No 315/93,) as “*any substance not intentionally added to food which is present in such food as a result of the production (including operations carried out in crop husbandry, animal husbandry and veterinary medicine), manufacture, processing, preparation, treatment, packing, packaging, transport or holding of such food, or as a result of environmental contamination*”. To protect public health, maximum levels in foodstuffs are set in the Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 for certain contaminants such as Nitrate, Mycotoxins, Metals, 3-monochloropropane-1,2-diol (3-MCPD) and glycidyl fatty acid esters, Dioxins and Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), PAHs, Melamine and its structural analogues, Inherent plant toxins and Perchlorate.

Nitrate is a naturally occurring compound that plays an important role in the nutrition and function of plants. Human exposure to nitrate is mainly through the consumption of vegetables, and to a lesser extent water and other foods. Nitrate determination is done by spectrophotometry.

In the Regulation No 1881/2006 maximum levels are set for a list of mycotoxins (aflatoxins, ochratoxin A, patulin, deoxynivalenol, zearalenone, fumonisins, T-2 and HT-2 toxin, citrinin, ergot sclerotia and ergot alkaloids) produced by different fungal species that can contaminate food commodities pre- and post-harvest or during storage. Food infection by mycotoxins depends on climate, temperature, moisture and humidity. The analytical techniques for the determination of aflatoxins, ochratoxin A, deoxynivalenol, zearalenone and fumonisins include purification through immunoaffinity columns and determination by LC coupled to tandem mass spectrometry and/or by LC with fluorescence detection. In the case of patulin, it is extracted by QUECHERS and then it is determined by LC coupled to tandem mass spectrometry.

Some toxins, like erucic acid, tropane alkaloids and hydrocyanic acid (including hydrocyanic acid bound in cyanogenic glycosides) are Inherent present in plants.

Perchlorate occurs naturally in the environment and as an environmental contaminant. Water, soil and fertilizers are considered to be potential sources of perchlorate contamination in food.

Moreover, metals such as arsenic, cadmium, lead and mercury are naturally occurring chemical compounds. They can be present at various levels in the environment, e.g., soil, water and atmosphere. Metals can also occur as residues in food because of their presence in

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 55

the environment, as a result of human activities such as farming, industry or car exhausts or from contamination during food processing and storage. For the determination of metals, microwave digestion of the samples is followed by analysis with graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry or FIAS. Arsenic is determined by hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometry. Inorganic tin can be potentially present in canned food in incorrectly manufactured tins, where tin present in the can has leached into the food. For the determination of tin, microwave digestion of the sample is followed by analysis with graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry.

Melamine is produced as a high-volume chemical. It can be present in food as a result of uses in food contact materials, including articles made of melamine-formaldehyde plastics, can coatings, paper and board and adhesives. It is determined by LC with fluorescence detection.

3-MCPD and Glycidyl fatty acid esters (GE) are substances formed during food processing, in particular, when refining vegetable oils at high temperatures.

For the determination of free 3-MCPD, the EN 14573:2005 method is used (Determination of 3-monochloropropane-1,2-diol by GC/MS). For the determination of 3-MCPD esters and glycidyl esters, the following method is used: «Analytical method for the trace determination of esterified 3- and 2-monochloropropanediol and glycidyl fatty acid esters in various food matrices, (Samaras et al., 2016)»,

Dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs are toxic chemicals that remain in the environment for years and build up at low levels in the food chain, usually in the fatty tissues of animals. Dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs are determined, applying international protocols of analysis (EPA 1613, EPA 1668), based on appropriate sample clean-up and determination by HRMS, using the isotope dilution method.

PAHs form a class of diverse organic compounds that may be formed and released during a variety of combustion and pyrolysis processes, including under certain food preparation and cooking conditions e.g., smoking, grilling and roasting. PAHs are determined with High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) with fluorescence detection (method based on ISO 15753: 2006). Alternatively, GC with mass spectrometry may be used.

REGULATION (EEU) 2020/2040 of 11 December 2020 amends Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 as regards maximum levels of pyrrolizidine alkaloids in certain foodstuffs. Pyrrolizidine alkaloids (PAs) are toxins which are produced naturally by a wide variety of plants. The determination of pyrrolizidine alkaloids is performed by LC coupled to tandem mass spectrometry, based on QuPPE method of the EU Reference Laboratories.

The setting of maximum levels for acrylamide in certain foods is currently under consideration. ([Acrylamide \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/infographic/Pages/infographic-acrylamide.aspx)). Acrylamide is a chemical that naturally forms in starchy food products during high-temperature cooking, including frying, baking, roasting and also

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 56

industrial processing, at +120 °C and low moisture. For acrylamide determination, the analyte is extracted with solid phase extraction cartridges, followed by isotopic dilution and determination by LC coupled to tandem mass spectrometry.

Contaminants are chemical hazards and contaminant levels must be kept as low as can be reasonably achieved by following good agricultural, fishery and manufacturing practices.

5.1.2.3 Consumer products

Non-food consumer products are goods that are determined for personal or household use and are not intended for consumption. The most common are personal care products, household products, beauty and cosmetics, electronics, clothing and toys. All these products include a variety of chemical substances, some of which can be proved harmful to human health such as endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs), as well as to the environment.

The main toxic chemicals that are commonly found in personal care products are: parabens, phthalates, bisphenols, sodium lauryl sulfate (sls) and sodium laureth sulfate (sles), formaldehyde and triclosan. These chemicals are used as preservatives, substances that can improve specific properties of the product or antimicrobial agents and recently have raised concerns (Guan et al., 2023; Pirard & Charlier, 2022). The analytical techniques of their determination include LC and GC coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (Martín-Pozo et al., 2021; Pirard & Charlier, 2022; Rocha et al., 2018; Ziółkowska et al., 2021).

In turn, cosmetics contain many common chemicals with the ones that are used in personal care products (Lamarca et al., 2019; Martín-Pozo et al., 2021). Moreover, people that use daily cosmetic products are exposed to metals as trace contaminants. Usually, the determination of metals is performed by inductively coupled plasma-mass-spectrometry (ICP-MS) (Bocca et al., 2014).

The last years, body art through tattooing and permanent make-up enjoy risen popularity in Western countries and thus, the concern of metal exposure (Kiszla et al., 2023; Kluger, 2015; Preetam et al., 2022). Moreover, metals found in clothing items can cause irritations through dermal contact (Rovira et al., 2015).

As for the household products, polyvinyl chloride (PVC), VOCs, perchloroethylene (PERC), triclosan, phthalates, bisphenol A, formaldehyde and some metals can be proved harmful. The analytical techniques for their determination include GC-MS, especially for VOCs (Lim & Shin, 2017; Wolkoff & Wilkins, 1994) and LC coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (Berthiller et al., 2006).

Metals, brominated flame retardants such as brominated dioxins and furans, phthalates and PVC can also be found in electronic devices (Famele et al., 2015; Gray et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2023).

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 57

Children may come last on this list, but they are still at the top of the protection measures. The presence of some chemicals in toys poses an extreme risk for the health and development of children. Coloring agents, plasticizers, fragrance allergens, nitrosamines, primary aromatic amines, brominated flame retardants, perfluorinated compounds are among the potential hazardous substances (Meng et al., 2020). Furthermore, trace metals, phthalates and bisphenol A are widely used in toys and childcare products (Ahmed et al., 2021; Finch et al., 2015; Negev et al., 2018).

5.1.2.4 Human biomonitoring

Human biomonitoring (HBM) studies evaluate the levels of different chemicals and their metabolites in human biological samples such as blood, urine and hair, making them an important tool on EWS for chemicals. In environmental and public health, HBM has grown to be a crucial technique for determining internal dosages of hazardous compounds and assessing the changes that occur in populations exposed to a specific environmental pollutant. (Hernández et al., 2019) Blood and urine are the most commonly used biofluids in HBM studies, since they are easily accessible and can provide stable measurements of the levels of the chemicals. Hair is another matrix that can be used in HBM studies, and it can provide information regarding the chronic exposure to chemicals. They contain a variety of biomarkers that reflect exposure to environmental and occupational toxicants, such as heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants, and other toxic chemicals (Esteban & Castaño, 2009). The placenta creates an interface between the mother and the fetus, by regulating the transfer of nutrients and acting as a barrier reducing the transmission of potentially hazardous compounds. Therefore, HBM studies can also give insight on the toxicity's processes and how exposure affects fetus development. Preventive interventions can be developed using this information to decrease the exposure of pregnant women and their fetus to dangerous substances and risk evaluations (Bocca et al., 2019).

Table 1: Potential matrices, compounds, and analytical techniques for HBM studies.

Matrix	Advantages	Limitations	Compounds measured in the matrix	Techniques
Blood, serum, plasma	There are well established standard operating procedures (SOPs) for sampling.	Invasive method (trained staff and special materials are required) Volume limitation and special conditions for transport and shipment	POPs, metals/trace elements, organic compounds, tobacco smoke. e.g.: alkylphenols, mercury, lead, BFRs, dioxins, water disinfection by-products, fluorinated compounds, organochlorine pesticides, organophosphate pesticides, phthalates, PCBs, dioxins.	Metabolomics (LC-MS, NMR), Chemical Analyses (GC-MS, ICP-MS), Gene expression analysis (Microarray, PCR)
Urine	Non-invasive method, easy to collect, no volume limitation	Composition of urine varies over time and according to the time of collection.	Metals/trace elements, organic compounds, tobacco smoke. Metabolites of environmental pollutants. e.g.: mercury, cadmium, arsenic, organochlorine compounds, BPA, organophosphate pesticides, parabens, phthalates, PAHs, benzene	Metabolomics (LC-MS), Chemical Analyses (GC-MS, ICP-MS)

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 58

Hair	Non-invasive method No special requirements for transport and storage Information about cumulative exposure during previous months.	Hair is exposed to the environment and can be contaminated. Potential variations with subject's hair colour, hair care or race may occur, and a special questionnaire is needed.	Metals/trace elements, POPs e.g.: total mercury, methylmercury, arsenic, cadmium, parabens, organochlorine compounds	Chemical Analyses (LC-MS, GC-MS, ICP-MS)
Saliva	Non-invasive, easy collection	The concentrations of analytes are lower than other matrices and as that sensitive analytical techniques are required. Furthermore, there are less publications on HBM applications.	Metals/trace elements, organic compounds, POPs, tobacco, e.g.: cadmium, phthalates, BPA, PCBs, dioxins	Metabolomics (LC-MS), Chemical Analyses (GC-MS, ICP-MS)
Placenta	Non-invasive, provides information about mother and child	Restricted to certain period of life	Metals/trace elements, POPs, organic compounds, e.g.: mercury, cadmium, lead, organochlorine pesticides, BPA, BFRs, dioxins, PCBs, PAHs, phthalates	Metabolomics (LC-MS, NMR), Chemical Analyses (GC-MS, ICP-MS)

5.1.3 Additional methods

5.1.3.1 Non-targeted screening analysis methods

5.1.3.1.1 Environmental samples and Human samples

The advent of high-throughput analytical instruments, like LC-HRMS, has significantly enhanced the capabilities of laboratories engaged in non-targeted screening. These cutting-edge technologies allow for the examination of a vast array of contaminants present in complex environmental and human samples. However, the high-throughput methods present a challenge as they produce a large number of signals, which are typically in the thousands per sample, making structural identification a significant challenge due to the extensive time and manual effort required (Gago-Ferrero et al., 2015). As a result, the application of prioritization strategies is an essential step in the NTS process, ensuring that efforts are focused on the most relevant part of the generated information (Alygizakis et al., 2019). The use of peak prioritization approaches in NTS can act as an EWS, helping to focus identification efforts on the most relevant chemicals (Brunner et al., 2019). Some examples of peak prioritization strategies that have been used in the literature are intensity-based criteria combined with a distinctive isotopic pattern (e.g. halogenated compounds) (Hug et al., 2014), mass defect to focus on molecular formulas outside the matrix domain in complex samples (Strynar et al., 2015), time series prioritization (prioritizing features that vary substantially over time) (Plassmann et al., 2016), and spatial variation using metabolic logic (Alygizakis et al., 2022) and multivariate statistics (Vanryckeghem et al., 2019). These strategies can be part of an EWS from chemicals. For example, time-trend analysis has been used in wastewater treatment plants to alert for pollution spills, which are events of direct disposal (e.g. due to illegal discharges) in the sewage system (Alygizakis et al., 2019). Especially powerful as an EWS can be the combination of NTS with bioanalytical tools, a method which is known as Effect Directed Analysis (EDA) (Brack, 2003). This method can be used to detect the chemicals which are the drivers of toxicity for a given sample.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 59

Furthermore, HRMS enables broad chemical profiling in biological samples, aiding in detecting numerous chemical features, including markers of human exposure. These markers are valuable for biomonitoring, environmental health studies, and risk assessment, potentially identifying CECs. Currently, CECs are predominantly monitored in environmental matrices like water, with limited focus in human biomonitoring due to lower abundance and collaboration challenges. However, evolving screening methods using HRMS offer a promising approach for identifying CECs in human studies. Within the HBM4EU project, suspect and NTS methods were developed for internal exposure markers, including the creation of the CECs screening and annotation database for CEC identification in humans via three key steps: aggregating, curating, and simulating metabolites. With 145,284 entries, this resource enables large-scale detection and prioritization of CECs in HRMS, benefiting exposome research by integrating diverse chemical and bioinformatic data. (Meijer et al., 2021; Pourchet et al., 2020) Additionally, the SPECIMEn study gathered over 2000 human urine samples from populations in five EU countries. The results from these samples could provide crucial data on exposure levels and help in adjusting regulations for chemical usage (Vitale et al., 2022) .

5.1.3.2 *Effect Directed Analysis*

EDA is particularly useful when there is a need to identify the cause of toxicity in complex environmental matrices, such as sediment or soil samples, where the toxicity may be due to the presence of many chemicals acting together (Brack, 2003). In such cases, EDA can help to identify the chemicals responsible for the toxicity and thereby facilitate the identification of hazardous chemicals at early stage. Additionally, EDA can be useful for identifying emerging contaminants, i.e., chemicals that may be present in environmental samples but are not typically analysed for in routine monitoring programs. EDA has been successfully applied to identify toxicants in a variety of environmental media, including airborne particulate matter, soils, sludge, sediments, effluents, surface water, and groundwater (Brack et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2023; Lopez-Herguedas et al., 2022). The core principle of EDA is to break down complex chemical mixtures into less complex subunits or fractions, which can then be subjected to bioassay testing to identify chemicals that contribute to toxicity. Ideally, this approach would allow for the complete separation of a mixture into fractions containing individual chemicals that could be individually tested for toxicity, followed by chemical characterization of the active fractions.

In practice, complete separation is rarely achieved. However, EDA still represents a valuable tool in toxicant discovery, particularly when combined with modern mass spectrometry-based chemical characterization methods such as HRMS. By using EDA to identify the toxic fractions of a mixture, researchers can focus their analytical efforts on characterizing only those chemicals that are most likely to be contributing to the observed toxicity. This approach can lead to more efficient and effective identification of toxicants in environmental mixtures.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 60

Multivariate statistics can be a useful tool in integrating chemical and toxicological information in EDA. Partial least square analysis is one such statistical method that can be used to identify chemical signals that co-vary with measured effects, effectively obtaining a "virtual fractionation" to identify candidate chemicals that may explain the effects (Hug et al., 2015). This approach can handle peaks from NTS and is not restricted to chemicals that have been previously identified. Analytical signals that correlate or co-vary with effects can be subjected to further structure elucidation, and if identified, integrated as candidate compounds in an iceberg modelling approach. This approach allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the potential drivers of toxicity in a sample, beyond just the chemicals that have been identified through traditional fractionation methods, although it can be expected that a relatively large number of samples would be needed for the approach to be successful.

Overall, EDA can be a powerful tool for identifying the cause of toxicity in complex environmental samples and for guiding the development of effective risk management strategies.

5.1.3.2.1 Effect-based methods: *in vivo* models

In vivo models investigate how living organisms, and their biological processes react to chemical exposure, including changes to their metabolism and gene expression. These models may be used to investigate the toxicity of novel compounds and assess possible negative consequences on human health. For instance, zebrafish are commonly used in *in vivo* studies due to their biological similarities to humans and their rapid life cycle. (Chakraborty et al., 2016) Consequently, by exposing the zebrafish to chemicals, any observed malfunctions can serve as an indicator that these chemicals may pose a potential threat to human health. Additionally, *in vivo* models can help detect biological pathways that are perturbed by chemical exposure, leading to an understanding of the mode of action of the chemicals and the determination of more effective methods to reduce their adverse effects. (Kumar & Jha, 2017) Transcriptomics is a method that can support EWS. More specifically, transcriptomics is used to study changes in gene expression in response to a particular stimulus. By examining the molecular changes caused by chemical exposure, transcriptomics can provide information about how a substance acts and aid in detecting potential health hazards. (Joseph, 2017) Additionally, metabolomics can study the metabolic changes that occur in response to a chemical exposure, providing information regarding the effects of these chemicals into the organism. (Ramirez et al., 2013)

5.1.3.2.2 Effect-based methods: *in vitro* models

In vitro models can support EWS for chemical risks by providing valuable information about the toxicity and potential health effects of chemicals. These models can include cellular assays that involve the study of the effects of chemicals on isolated cells or cell cultures. These assays

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 61

can be used to evaluate the toxicity of chemicals and to screen new chemicals for safety and efficacy. In order to provide more detailed information about the potential health effects of exposure to a chemical, cellular assays with specific endpoints, such as genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, or developmental toxicity can be used. Additionally, cells can be cultured to form 3D structures that more closely resemble the organization and function of tissues *in vivo*, allowing the study of the chemical on cell behaviour and tissue organization which cannot be easily studied in 2D cell cultures (Cacciamali et al., 2022).

In vitro studies usually include the determination of the metabolic and gene expression changes that occur after the exposure to a particular chemical. Transcriptomics and metabolomics can be used to evaluate the potential toxicity of new chemicals and through these studies, we can get an early indication of the potential risks associated with the exposure. Moreover, by analyzing the changes in the biological pathways, potential health hazards can be identified, and a better understanding of the biological mechanisms involved in chemical toxicity can be retrieved. (Ardisasmitta et al., 2022; Cuykx et al., 2019) Another *in vitro* method that would be very useful in the EWS is the Organ-on-a-chip system, which is a system that can mimic the functions of human organs and can be used to study the effects of chemicals on multiple organ systems. (Leung et al., 2022) Finally, High-Throughput Screening (HTS) assays can be used to screen large numbers of chemicals for potential toxicity, helping to identify potential health hazards quickly and efficiently. (Entzeroth et al., 2009) HTS assays are used for screening of different types of libraries, including combinatorial chemistry, genomics, protein, and peptide libraries. It is of vital importance, because parallel and combinatorial chemical synthesis generates a vast number of novel compounds. The HTS method is more frequently utilized in combination with analytical techniques like NMR or coupled methods such as LC-MS/MS. (Szymański et al., 2012)

5.1.3.2.3 NAMs

New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) are defined as any technology, methodology or approach that does not use animals and can provide information on chemical hazard and human risk assessment. (Dent et al., 2018) They can be used as alternatives to traditional animal testing and include *in silico* methods (such as Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship - QSAR and machine learning models), *in vitro* (cell cultures and organoids) and *ex vivo* (omics applications) approaches. (Gwinn et al., 2020; Malinowska et al., 2022; Pamies et al., 2022; Thompson et al., 2021) NAMs are not necessarily newly developed methods, rather, it is their application to regulatory decision-making or replacement of a conventional testing requirement that is new. NAMs can mimic human biology and provide mechanistic information about how a chemical may cause toxicity in humans. (Stucki et al., 2022)

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 62

Omics technologies can provide information about the molecular changes in response to chemical exposure and help identify potential toxicity pathways. Omics (transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics) can be used to identify the molecular mechanisms of toxicity and evaluate the effects of exposure to multiple chemicals and lead to the development of novel Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs). (Miccoli et al., 2022) By combining the omics with other NAMs, such as *in silico* models and high-throughput screening, a better understanding of the toxicology of the chemicals can be achieved, by linking the exposure to adverse outcomes and facilitate the creation of novel AOPs. (Ram et al., 2022; Sturla et al., 2014) Additionally, Artificially Intelligence (AI) can be one of the most crucial NAMs used in EWS, as it can process and analyze the data obtained from omics analyses and identify potential key events and biological pathways for the development of AOPs (Blümmel et al., 2023).

5.2 Modelling tools

5.2.1 Role of modelling tools in EWS

Modelling tools are a broad category of software and algorithms that are used to simulate the properties and behaviour of chemicals. These tools can take many forms, including computational models, mathematical equations, and computer simulations. They are essential in an EWS for chemicals by providing valuable information about potential chemical hazards and predicting the chemical exposome before compounds are widely distributed. Computational tools will evaluate the impact of terms of use of chemicals on human health and the environment. This information can be integrated to guide decision-making and to develop strategies and guidelines to respond to hazards.

One of the most important applications of computational tools in an EWS is the simulation of the behaviour of chemicals in different environments. For example, Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models can be used to predict the movement and metabolism of a chemical in the human body. Distribution of a chemical is of vital importance, as it provides knowledge on how tissues are affected, or how blood or urine concentrations can be translated into brain, liver, or nervous system concentrations. PBPK models are an intermediate tier in the overall computational methodology (**Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**) that can be used to predict the behaviour of chemicals in different environments.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 63

Figure 4. Source to effect continuum.

One more example with a crucial role in EWS is the environmental fate models. These are tools that can be used to predict the movement and degradation of a chemical in the environment. Environmental fate models will be at the beginning of the calculations and will provide input to the rest of the tools of EWS. These simulations can help policy makers identify potential risks and hazards associated with a chemical, such as toxicity to humans and animals or environmental persistence. QSAR applications are one more illustration of how modelling tools will contribute to a novel EWS.

Computational algorithms and analysis tools are also included in the modelling tools. Another advantage provided by the PARC EWS is the ability to analyse large amounts of data on the properties and behaviour of chemicals, which can help to identify patterns and trends that would be difficult to discern by other means. An effort will be implemented in this direction by automating the analysis procedure. For example, machine learning algorithms can be trained on large datasets of chemical information to distinguish potential toxic properties of a chemical.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 64

Last but not least comes **risk assessment**. Computational simulations can also be used to assess the potential risk of a chemical on human health and the environment. This can be done by using all the tools that have been developed in a plethora of projects under the European Commission (EC) umbrella and briefly presented in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** to evaluate the terms of use of a product. As a result, interacting with Task 8.3 is indispensable in order to take advantage of the provided knowledge.

Figure 5. Array of exposure and hazard tools available within PARC consortium.

It is obvious that without modelling tools, an EWS cannot operate efficiently. It will not be able to evaluate terms of use of chemicals and provide signals if a chemical is a potential hazard. It would only be able to rely on experimental testing and observational data to detect possible risks and hazards associated with a compound. As a result, the term "early signal" is weakened. In addition, the absence of the computational part of an EWS would likely limit its ability to predict the properties and behaviour of chemicals before they are synthesized and tested. It would also be more resource-intensive, as a large number of chemicals would need to be synthesized and tested in order to identify potential risks and hazards.

All of these examples illustrate how modelling tools can be used to predict and simulate the properties and behaviours of chemicals in different environments, and identify potential risks and hazards associated with a compound. Innovative modelling tools can play a crucial role in an EWS for chemicals by providing valuable information about the properties and behaviours of chemicals, identifying potential risks and hazards, analysing large amounts of data, and

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 65

prioritizing chemicals for further testing and development. This information can be used to make more informed decisions about which chemicals to pursue, how to prioritize them, and how to develop them safely and effectively with the aim of creating a safer, greener, and more sustainable future. All the tools that will be integrated into the PARC EWS are discussed in further detail in the following sections.

5.2.2 Environmental fate models

The environmental fate is a key component to properly assess the impact of a substance in the environment. Indeed, this is requested in several regulatory perspectives, for instance to characterize if a substance is persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT) or very persistent and very toxic (vPvB). More recently, the interest has been put also on mobility. This kind of information is highly relevant. If a substance is stable, it will remain in the environment for a long period, and thus all the potentially adverse effect can be generated over a longer period. If a substance is mobile, in the air or in water, it will affect a much larger geographical area than a substance which is not mobile.

The US EPA has been a pioneer in the development of tools to predict the fate, introducing for instance the EPISuite platform. It has to be noticed that in different countries the interest is towards different environmental conditions. Thus, for instance, in Europe the persistence has to be evaluated for soil, sediment and water, and thus the air long-range transport may result less relevant. Furthermore, unfortunately the threshold values defined in different regulations are different. Thus, it may happen that relatively large collections of data are available from studies done in Canada, where the thresholds for the definition of persistence are different from those used in Europe.

Beyond models on persistence and air transport, there are models on ready biodegradability, and behaviour within waste water treatment plants. Furthermore, the models available may be different because they address different categories of substances. We will present here some examples, in particular those which will be more easily used within PARC.

IRFMN has developed several environmental fate models. They have been implemented within the VEGA platform (<https://www.vegahub.eu/>) Models available are:

- ready biodegradability
- persistence (sediment) - qualitative
- persistence (sediment) - quantitative
- persistence (soil) - qualitative
- persistence (soil) - quantitative
- persistence (water) - qualitative
- persistence (water) - quantitative
- Air half-life

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 66

- Environmental degradation pathways
- Bioconcentration (BCF) - several models

5.2.3 Exposure models

Exposure modelling in an EWS for chemicals is a comprehensive process that includes identifying populations at risk, estimating exposure levels, identifying sources of exposure, improving risk management decisions, and supporting research and the development of new methodologies. It is essential because it provides critical information about the potential exposure of humans and the environment to chemicals, which is crucial for identifying potential risks and hazards associated with chemicals early on and for designing effective risk reduction measures.

Furthermore, exposure assessment also includes an evaluation of the uncertainties associated with the data and the methods used. This allows for the identification of areas where additional data is needed and the development of strategies to reduce uncertainties. This can include the measurement of chemicals in air, water, soil, food, or consumer products, as well as the measurement of chemicals in human blood, urine, or other biological samples. Exposure estimation includes all routes of exposure, the duration of exposure, and the frequency of exposure. In addition, this type of assessment is vital to identify sources of exposure, such as industrial facilities, consumer products, or environmental contamination. As can be seen, this is a widely discussed manner of an innovative EWS.

Another key component here is the continuously improved management decisions based on the data collected. The obtained data can be used to inform risk management decisions, such as the development of exposure limits, the selection of risk reduction measures, and the design of surveillance programs as well as an evaluation tool in an EWS. Moreover, exposure models can lead to the development of new sampling and analytical methods for the identification of new exposure pathways. This can help to improve the accuracy and precision of exposure models and to identify new areas of concern. Exposure to chemicals can occur through various routes, such as inhalation, dermal contact, ingestion, and injection. EWS should also be able to implement multiple exposure scenarios. Exposure can occur in different settings, such as in the workplace, in the home, and in the community, and different scenarios may be associated with different levels of exposure. For example, exposure to a chemical used in manufacturing may be higher for workers in a factory compared to the general population living nearby. It should also be mentioned that mixture exposure models should also be included in an EWS, as these scenarios closely approximate real-life issues, as well as scenarios that integrate long-term exposure.

Chemicals can be present at varying levels in different locations and at different times, and exposure levels can also differ depending on a person's occupation, lifestyle, and other

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 67

factors. It is essential to take these variations into account when evaluating exposure levels and potential risks. For instance, a chemical may be present at higher concentrations in an industrial area compared to a residential area, and a person who works in an industrial area may have higher exposure levels compared to a person who resides in a residential area. Additionally, exposure levels may vary seasonally depending on factors such as weather, temperature, and the use of consumer products. This should be considered an important aspect of the chemical's persistence and bioaccumulation potential. Persistent chemicals remain in the environment for prolonged periods of time and can accumulate in the food chain, leading to higher exposure levels. Bioaccumulation can also occur in the human body, resulting in high levels of exposure even at low external exposure levels. Furthermore, exposure assessment should also include an evaluation of the chemical's toxicity and the potential health effects associated with exposure. This information is used to determine the levels of exposure that are considered safe and to identify potential health risks. In addition, it is important to involve multiple stakeholders in the exposure assessment process, such as regulatory agencies, industry, and community groups. This can help to ensure that the exposure assessment is comprehensive and inclusive, and that the results are relevant and useful for decision-making.

It is now obvious that exposure assessment in an EWS for chemicals is a multi-step process that includes several stages, such as planning, data collection, data analysis, and interpretation. In the planning stage, the objectives of the exposure assessment are defined, the populations and chemicals of concern are identified, and the sampling and analytical methods are chosen. In the data collection stage, samples are collected from the environment, food, water, air, and consumer products. Biomonitoring samples such as blood, urine, hair, or nails may also be collected to measure the levels of chemicals in the human body. In the data analysis stage, the samples are analysed using appropriate analytical methods to measure the levels of chemicals. The data is then cleaned, and quality assurance and quality control procedures are applied. In the modelling level, data identification computes the dynamics of exposure to humans or the environment. This step is crucial as it serves as input to PBPK models, the next model tier in the PARC EWS computational procedure, in order to calculate the internal exposure i.e., the distribution of a compound in the human body. In the interpretation stage, the data is used to estimate exposure levels, identify sources of exposure, and assess the potential health or environmental risks associated with the chemicals. The data is also used to evaluate the effectiveness of risk reduction measures and make recommendations for future actions.

Last but not least, it is important to note that exposure assessment is an ongoing process that requires continuous monitoring and updating of data as new information becomes available. This is crucial for an EWS, as it allows for the rapid identification of new risks and the implementation of appropriate risk reduction measures. Additionally, the use of high-

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 68

throughput analytics and the integration of data from multiple sources, such as environmental monitoring, biomonitoring, and epidemiology studies, can enhance the accuracy and completeness of exposure assessments.

5.2.4 PBPK/TK models

A critical component in understanding exposure is data on dose at target, i.e., the dose that reach the target for the molecular initiating event or key event in an AOP. Understanding processes of adsorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) are key for determining fate of chemicals in biota and their hazard. ADME processes can be modelled using physiology based pharmacokinetic or toxicokinetic (PBPK/TK) models to follow uptake and depuration processes over time. These models are based on combinations of differential equations and require detailed information on physiology of the studied organism and chemical specific information. Physiology data covers organ specific information including volumes, blood flows, reproduction, growth etc. The models are chemical specific and requires information on e.g., partitioning between blood and studied tissues, and metabolism and excretion processes. Models are developed for humans and rodents but also for aquatic biota including several fish species. Data required for model parametrization can derived experimentally but also using computational methods including QSAR/QSPRs. Model development is currently moving towards higher resolution in number of organs, ionization processes, and new species but also towards high-throughput modelling. New techniques like read-across along with PBPK can be helpful in identifying the accumulation or disposition of new chemicals at early stages. The latter development is an opening for inclusion into an EWS to inform on dose at target for emerging chemicals or yet unexplored chemicals. Specialized models like pregnancy, gestational, and lactational PBPK can predict the risk for fetus and infants helping in early prediction of disease. Additionally, integrating PBPK/TK models with exposure assessment and systems biology model can also help in developing EWS by providing information regarding the toxicity of emerging chemicals.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 69

Figure 6. Multi-compartment PBPK model with 12 compartments. Excretion of the compound is from feces via gut, urine via kidney and breath via lung respectively.

5.2.5 Systems biology models

Systems biology models are mathematical models that aim to simulate the complex interactions between different biological processes and systems. They are the missing link between genotype and phenotype incorporating multi scale biological networks. These models involve quantitative predictions and can be an important tool in EWS for chemicals, as they can provide valuable insights into the potential health risks associated with chemical exposure. Xenobiotics affect human health by alteration in cellular uptake and efflux controlled by membrane transporter protein, interaction of chemical and metabolites by tissue macromolecules, immune response activation, metabolic transformations and much more. To understand these interactions at different level of biological organizations, molecular and cellular targets, different SB models are required (mentioned below):

- Predictive modelling:

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 70

Systems biology models use mathematical equations and computational methods to simulate the interactions between different biological systems and processes, and they can be used to predict the effects of chemicals on the body at the tissue, cellular, and molecular levels. This information can be integrated to inform the response to new potential threats to human health and the environment. These mathematical models incorporate metabolic control analysis (MCA), flux balance analysis (FBA) and elementary model analysis (EMA) to understand network associated toxicity pathway and much more.

- *In silico* testing:

Systems biology models can be used as a tool for *in silico* testing, which is a virtual or computer-based method of testing the effects of chemicals without conducting animal or human experiments. This allows for the prediction of the effects of chemicals without the need for expensive and time-consuming animal or human experiments.

- Understanding the mechanism of toxicity:

SB model often contains multiple pathways to elucidate the crosstalk occurring at the cellular level after xenobiotic exposure. These SB models can be simplified and converted to AOPs. They provide pieces of information regarding the Molecular Initiating Events (MIE) and potential key events (KEs) leading to an adverse outcome. They follow the holistic Mode of Action (MoA) that a disruptor has when a human is exposed to a xenobiotic. As a result of that exposure, risk can be identified, and the compound can be evaluated for its terms of use. In the same direction, systems biology models also provide the identification of genetic and epigenetic changes. These changes include anomalies in the genome, transcriptome, proteome, or metabolome of a human and the way these processes are regulated. Experimental data along with computational models like SB can help reduce the experiments required to define potential MIE and KEs. SB model provides quantitative risk assessment and insights about biological events occurring in the cell. For instance, modelling the neurological signalling pathway helps in evaluating the experimentally relevant relationship between proteins and related perturbations that can help connect critical factors statistically relevant as common signalling mechanisms. Moreover, the integrated PBPK/SB model can help build quantitative AOPs (qAOP). qAOP provides quantitative time-course prediction and dose-response aiding regulatory decision-making. It also provides quantitative understanding of the transition from critical key events as well as a quantitative prediction for the severity of AO helping in detecting the risk at early stages.

- Potential Biomarkers Identification:

Systems biology models can be used to identify potential biomarkers, which are molecular indicators of exposure or effects that can be used to monitor exposure or assess the health effects of chemicals. MoA will provide very useful insights for classifying compounds and

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 71

recognizing their toxicity patterns. Furthermore, potential biomarker identification includes key metabolic pathways that play a crucial role in human toxicity patterns.

- Dose – Response relationships:

Systems biology models can be used to model the relationship between the dose of a chemical and the resulting biological response, which can be informed to a chemical distribution and provide early warning signs of a potential hazard. Sometime the interaction of the compound with the receptor is not linear, in such cases complex SB model help in predicting the response or toxicity at a particular dose/exposure. Integrating PK with SB model for dose-response aid in including processes like slow receptor binding, chemical-chemical interactions, disease progression, enzyme kinetics, target site distribution, bind and activation of receptor etc. with inter- and intraindividual variability helping in predicting early risk in human.

- Understanding the interplay between different chemicals:

Biological models can be used as a tool to identify interactions between chemicals at different states and levels of biological processes. It includes cases where there is all-or-none type of effect as sometime interaction between xenobiotics with competitive mechanism may produce additive response (all effect) or non-competitive mechanism with antagonistic action (none effect). This procedure involves the integration of SB and AI methodologies and PK to explain such phenomenon. As can be seen, this is a very important component that an innovative EWS should have.

- Integration with all the other tiers described.

They can be integrated with other models, such as exposure models, PBPK models, toxicokinetics, AI algorithms, and bioinformatics, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the effects of chemicals on the human body.

Finally, it is obvious that systems biology models are a tool that can improve risk assessment and can be incorporated into a modern EWS functioning as an intermediate step to support the decision-making process. These models can address biological perturbations in a multidimensional manner, delivering very useful evidence through multiple outputs for the next tier's methodologies, integrating inputs from previous layers.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 72

Figure 7. Integrated Translational approach for risk Assessment. These models can act as a tool for translation and prediction of risk to human species.

5.2.6 Bioinformatics

Bioinformatics is an essential component of an innovative EWS as the one that will be developed in the framework of PARC. EWS aims to identify and respond to potential public health threats as early as possible, and bioinformatics plays a crucial role in achieving this goal by providing tools and techniques for analysing and interpreting large amounts of data related to exposure and hazard. Informatics algorithms will provide the edges and the nodes with other scientific communities (Statistics, Mathematics, Biology, Physics, Chemistry, etc.) in a machine-readable format. This approach will enable the system to be able to take decisions regarding the jeopardy of a compound to public health.

One of the main ways bioinformatics can contribute to a successful EWS is through the use of tools to scrutinize genetic information, as well as metabolic data. This information will provide evidence to link a compound with an adverse outcome. In addition, bioinformatic algorithms will also deliver the interconnections between a decision network that will evaluate a chemical and its terms of use. Omics data is a key ingredient to achieve this.

The use of omics data is becoming increasingly necessary, as it is continued encounters with new chemicals and their potential impacts on human health and the environment, or existing chemicals and possible effects that have not been determined yet. Omics technologies, such as genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, provide a comprehensive and holistic understanding of the biological effects of chemicals, allowing for the detection of potential health risks at an early stage.

One of the key advantages of using omics data in EWS is the ability to identify specific molecular mechanisms and pathways that are affected by a chemical. This information can be

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 73

used to predict potential health risks, such as cancer or reproductive toxicity, and to design targeted interventions to mitigate these risks. This will be one of the key attributes of the PARC EWS. Additionally, omics data can be used to identify biomarkers of exposure and early indicators of toxicity, which can be used to detect the presence of a chemical in the environment.

Despite these advantages, there are also some limitations to using omics data in EWS. One limitation is that the data generated by omics technologies can be complex and difficult to interpret, requiring specialized expertise and sophisticated analytical tools. This venture will be carried out using innovative analysis algorithms that will be developed in the framework of Work Packages 4 and 5. Omics technologies can be directly connected with EWS if not provided by the user, or they can be retrieved from linked databases in order to be meta-analysed and provide useful insights. Information derived from omics technologies can be used to identify potential risks and to develop strategies for EWS.

Furthermore, bioinformatics also includes the term "Biostatistics," an important component of an EWS as well. Statistics provide methodological tools to identify patterns and trends in data and to make predictions about the potential health risks associated with exposure to a chemical. Strictly speaking, biostatistics can also be used to determine the level of uncertainty associated with the predictions that will be provided by AI models, which is essential for making informed risk management decisions. Last but not least, tools such as score matching, regression analysis, and sensitivity analysis can be used to control these uncertainties.

Finally, bioinformatics can provide tools related to possible chemicals of concern. Molecular docking is a bioinformatic technique that can be used to predict the potential health risks associated with exposure to a chemical without the need for extensive animal testing. Additionally, informatics can be used to classify and prioritize chemicals that may be of concern based on their structural and chemical properties, allowing for targeted testing and risk assessment in cases where *in silico* tools cannot provide a clear understanding of a MoA that a chemical has.

5.2.7 QSARs models

QSAR modeling gives an opportunity to identify specific structural features of chemicals, so called structural alerts, responsible for inducing biological activity or adverse outcomes of investigated chemical substances. Development of QSAR models utilizes application of classical linear regression-based methods to advanced machine learning methodologies, which allow for multidimensional analysis of structural and physicochemical characteristics of chemicals, in relation to the observed biological effect(s) on molecular, cellular, tissue or organism level. QSAR models are constructed based on available, usually limited data from *in vivo* or *in vitro* experiments. Complementary input for development QSAR model is a

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 74

structural and physicochemical characteristic of tested chemicals expressed numerically through a set of explanatory variables i.e., descriptors, often directly associated with structural alerts. Depending on the applied methodology, QSAR model takes the form of a mathematical linear/non-linear function, or set of logical rules, where interdependencies between descriptors are considered. Recent advanced methods in QSAR such as pharmacophore modelling is widely accepted in pharmaceuticals domain. Pharmacophore modelling, apart from considering the physiochemical properties of ligand, it also accounts the binding/interaction capacity ligand with the receptor. Pharmacophore modelling can be used a next step after QSAR to further narrow down the chemical space being used for investigation (Kumar et al., 2022).

Consequently, developed QSAR models enable to enhance the knowledge and mechanistic interpretation of molecular initiating events and key events leading to the adverse outcome. Moreover, compiled QSAR models can be applied in a virtual screening of a large library of untested chemical substances to forecast their biological effects. QSAR modeling partly fulfils the 3Rs' principles proposed by Russel and Burch (*The Principles of Humane Experimental Technique*, 1959), aimed at replacement, reduction, and refinement of animal testing. Additional benefits of QSAR modeling approach are reduction of financial costs, time and workload of research on chemicals testing. Currently, there are available numerous QSAR tools with a wide applicability domain or designed to specific group of substances for prediction of physicochemical properties, as well as toxicological and ecotoxicological effects. However, there is a constant need for development of models adjusted to assessment of high concern chemicals and enabling the identification of such.

As an example, IRFMN has developed the VEGAHUB platform containing *in silico* tools for QSAR, read-across, risk assessment, substitution, prioritization and screening. The QSAR models are called VEGA models, and they are about 100. Models are divided into six categories: human toxicity, ecotoxicity, fate and distribution, physical-chemical properties, human PBPK and ecological PBPK. With VEGA is possible to get a clear measurement of the reliability of the prediction and also visualize the most similar compounds of your target substance, for a read-across assessment. Indeed, each model in VEGA provides the prediction, and in addition the evaluation on the reliability of the prediction. This is done through the so called Applicability Domain Index (ADI), which is a quantitative value from 0 to 1. In practice there are thresholds where which indicate if the prediction is of good, moderate or low reliability, which vary on the model, but are about > 0.85 for good, < 0.7 for low, and in between it is moderate. This index is calculated automatically based on several parameters, which are also shown, so that the user can easily judge the possible critical aspects for a certain prediction for the substance of interest.

VEGA also provides the most similar compounds, and this information is used for the ADI, but can be used independently for read-across. Furthermore, VEGA shows the chemical moieties

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 75

which are associated to the effect when the model uses them. This particular information can be used for reasoning. The user should use all the three lines of evidence given by VEGA: the prediction, the read-across and the reasoning. In all cases, when experimental information is available, it is used and shown.

In VEGAHUB there are also several tools for read-across. We already mentioned that the VEGA models can be used for read-across. Another system is called ToxRead. It has modules for tens of properties. It shows the most similar compounds and groups of similar substances also according to the presence of particular issue, such as presence of a structural alert or a particular property associated to the effect of interest, such as a logP value exceeding a certain value associated to bioconcentration.

VERA is another tool for read-across, which will be available in February 2023, which cluster substances in groups according to different criteria and then evaluates similar substances present in different clusters.

In Q1 of 2023 a new software will be added, integrating the results from QSAR and read-across, within a weight-of-evidence strategy.

The VEGA models are also at the basis of other software systems, such as JANUS and VERMEER. JANUS, available on the VEGAHUB website (<https://www.vegahub.eu/>), is a tool to prioritize and screen substances, considering PBT (Persistent, Bioaccumulative and Toxic) and CMR (Carcinogenic, Mutagenic and Reprotoxic) substances, as well as chemicals supposed to be endocrine disruptors. In all cases, when experimental information is available, it is used and shown.

The VERMEER tools are specific for risk assessment. There are several tools depending on the exposure scenario. For instance, one is for cosmetics. The user provides the information about the ingredients in a cosmetic product. The VERMEER tool evaluates skin permeation to get the internal exposure and uses the VEGA model for the hazard information. In all cases, when experimental information is available, it is used and shown.

The ToxEraser tool provides suggested alternatives for cosmetic ingredients which are of concern.

The LIFE CONCERT REACH project (<https://www.life-concertreach.eu/>) established a network of tools, such as VEGA, Danish QSAR Database, OCHEM and AMBIT.

OPERA, a tool developed by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA), contains QSAR/QSPR models for chemical properties of environmental interest.

OECD QSAR Toolbox is a software platform developed in collaboration with the European Chemicals Agency to support governments, chemical industry, academia and other stakeholders in the hazard assessment of chemical substances. The Toolbox enables identification of structural alerts, potential mechanisms and mode of action of the target

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 76

chemical based on the category of chemicals (source compounds) and predicts the toxicological or ecotoxicological data gaps.

The *in silico* models are more and more used also within regulatory contexts. For instance, European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) used QSAR models to screen pre-registered substances and identify substances of higher concern, using three platform, including VEGA, the Danish (Q)SAR Database and a tool from the US EPA.

EFSA is using *in silico* predictions in some Units, for instance used VEGA to evaluate food contact materials, and uses VEGA, the Danish (Q)SAR Database and the TEST software from the US EPA.

The German UBA funded projects to develop JANUS for prioritization (see above) and toDIVINE, a software developed by IRFMN, for the integration of read-across and *in silico* models.

5.2.8 Text Mining tools

Text mining is an essential component to the development of PARC EWS for chemicals because it allows for the automated extraction and analysis of large amounts of information from various sources such as scientific and grey literature, news articles, and government reports. This can help to identify potential hazards associated with the use of chemicals and facilitate the development of appropriate regulations and policies. For example, the recently developed AI tool, named AOP-helpFinder (<https://aop-helpfinder.u-paris-sciences.fr/>; Jaylet T, Coustillet T, Jornod F, Margaritte-Jeannin P, Audouze K., Environ Int. 2023 Jul;177:108017. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2023.108017.) may be adapted for use in model development for EWS.

In addition, mining techniques can be used to extract information on the properties and uses of chemicals, such as toxicity, persistence in the environment, and potential for bioaccumulation. This can help to identify chemicals that may be harmful to human health or the environment. Furthermore, mining techniques can feed QSAR models with data in case that information regarding the corresponding chemical is not available. One addition key component is the identification of potential exposure pathways for chemicals, such as through food, water, or air. This can help to find out populations that may be at risk for exposure to harmful chemicals.

Moreover, the text mining tools have the potential of the identification of transformation products crucial for assessing compound degradation and environmental risks. These tools help aggregate, curate, and simulate metabolites, enhancing the database's capacity to include a wider array of known transformation reactions. The "ShinyTPs" application, designed for visualizing and curating text-mined chemical reactions, can contribute significantly by

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 77

facilitating curation of transformation products and associated reactions, potentially serving as highly curated data sets for machine learning models. (Palm et al., 2023)

Text mining can be used to extract information on existing regulations and policies for chemicals, such as restrictions on use or disposal recognizing gaps in regulation and informing the development of new regulations and policies. Moreover, one of the aims here is not just the reporting of a potential hazard but the identification of a potential alternative material, safer and more sustainable. This can help to promote the development of new technologies that are less reliant on harmful chemicals.

In summary, text mining is essential to the development of an EWS for chemicals because it allows for the automated extraction and analysis of large amounts of information from various sources, which can help to identify potential hazards early on, extract information on chemical properties, identify potential exposure pathways, extract information on regulations and policies, and identify potential alternative materials.

Figure 8. Text Mining based architecture for early warning system.

5.2.9 Other AI models

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an essential component of an innovative EWS. It can improve the capabilities of an EWS for chemicals by providing more accurate and faster detection of potential chemical hazards. All other computational algorithms that have been mentioned incorporate artificial intelligence patterns. AI algorithms can be used to analyse large amounts of data, including sensor readings and weather patterns, to identify outliers and anomalies that may indicate a chemical incident. Additionally, AI can be used to predict the impact that a chemical might have on human health and the environment, helping to improve response times and reduce the risk of harm.

Some of the tools utilized with AI models are the use of deep learning. Deep learning is a subset of machine learning that involves the use of neural networks, designed to simulate the way the human brain processes information. These networks consist of layers of

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 78

interconnected nodes, called neurons, that process and transmit information. These neural networks can be trained to analyse large and complex data sets, such as those generated by high-throughput screening or human biomonitoring initiatives, making them well-suited for use in EWS for chemicals. These "smart" algorithms can be trained to identify patterns and trends in data that may not be visible to the human eye, which can help to detect chemicals that might be of concern, providing early insights into risks associated with chemical treatment. Additionally, deep learning can be used to predict the potential health risks associated with exposure to a chemical without the need for extensive animal testing, a very helpful component for obtaining early signals. Another advantage of using deep learning in EWS is the association with QSAR models and the ability to distinguish and prioritize chemicals that are of concern. Given that a model is trained to analyse data from a variety of sources, such as chemical and toxicological databases, scientific literature, and experimental data, they can be a very accurate tool based on the pre-processing procedures that are selected. Hence, ANNs are currently used for classification and regression modelling. For example, a neural network could be trained on a dataset containing the chemical structures and known toxicity of a set of chemicals, and then be used to predict the toxicity of new chemicals based on their structures. This is also known as QSAR.

Figure 9. AI models for processing different data types

Furthermore, there are several AI methodologies that could be implemented through PARC EWS. For instance, Random Forest is an ensemble learning method that operates by constructing a multitude of decision trees at training time and outputting the class that is the mode of the classes (classification) or mean prediction (regression) of the individual trees. Random Forest can be used to classify chemicals based on their structural and chemical properties, identify chemicals that might be of concern, and prioritize them for further testing

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 79

and risk assessment. Random Forest is a powerful tool for modelling and predicting chemical toxicity. Also, Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are an artificial learning methodology that can help with the identification of patterns between chemicals and their toxicity actions. SVMs are a type of supervised machine learning algorithm that can be used to classify chemicals based on their structural and chemical properties. They are based on the idea of finding a hyperplane that best separates different classes of data. They can also be used to predict the potential health risks associated with exposure to a chemical.

Last but not least come Bayesian Networks (BN). They are a type of probabilistic graphical model that can be used to model the relationships between different chemical properties and potential health risks. They can be used to identify chemicals that may be harmful to human health and the environment and to predict the risks associated with exposure to a compound. Bayesian networks are particularly useful for modelling complex systems where there are many interrelated variables and uncertain relationships.

All these models are based on the same principle, but they have different architectures and methodologies. It is worth noting that these AI models are not mutually exclusive; they can be combined and integrated to improve the performance of the EWS. Certainly, an EWS for chemical hazards is designed to detect and alert authorities and the public to the presence of harmful chemicals in the environment. By incorporating AI, such a system can become more accurate and efficient in detecting chemical incidents and predicting their spread.

It is worth mentioning that there are several ways in which AI models can lead to a state-of-the-art EWS. Some specific ways include a) automated sensor data analysis, b) predictive modelling, as has been mentioned in detail previously, c) improved automated monitoring and reporting processes for chemical incidents and reducing the potential for human error, and d) smart alarm systems that aim to send early signals. Unsupervised learning is the key to succeeding with all these statements.

Unsupervised learning is a technique in which a model is trained on an unlabelled dataset. In the context of an EWS for chemicals, an unsupervised learning model could be trained on a dataset of sensor readings and *in silico* data patterns, without any labels indicating whether a signal needs to be paid attention to or not. Unsupervised learning might also be beneficial in the case of self-trained models. These models will be incorporated into PARC EWS while new data will continuously be produced and integrated into the system through databases (KEGG, STICH, CTD, etc.). Unsupervised learning provides robustness to the system and helps in detecting new patterns.

One more advantage of using unsupervised learning is feature extraction. This process is applied to identify relevant features in the data, a classification modelling technique for chemicals present in the environment. Feature extraction is carried out using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and autoencoders. It should also be noted that the combination of

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 80

reinforcement learning with unsupervised learning will significantly improve the overall performance of the EWS.

Finally, some specific artificial intelligence algorithms that could possibly be introduced in PARC EWS can be seen below:

- RNNs (Recurrent Neural Networks) and LSTM (Long-Short Term Memory) networks can analyse timeseries data.
- Large Language Models (LLM) trained on biomedical text can be used for unstructured information processing.
- Ontology assisted normalization of events.
- Multi – model data integration. Data derived from multiple sources.
- Real – time data processing for quick responses to potential hazards.
- Adaptability: AI-based systems are adaptable and can continuously learn from new data, which allows the EWS to improve over time.
- Handling non-linear relationship: AI is particularly good at modelling non-linear relationships in data, which can be useful for understanding probable jeopardies.
- Automation: AI-based systems can automate many of the tasks involved in monitoring and analysing data, reducing the need for human intervention, and minimizing the risk of human error.
- Cost-efficiency: AI-based systems can help to reduce the costs associated with monitoring and analysing data, by automating many of the tasks.

Vast developments have been witnessed the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in addressing food safety issues (Xinxin Wang et al., 2022). Using “Big Data” has become a new trend in identifying early warning signals and emerging issues with regard to food safety risks (Jin et al., 2020). In addition to the conventional food safety monitoring data, more diverse data sources (e.g., sensor data, image data, text data) are being used as data inputs for the AI food safety models (Jin et al., 2020). Moreover, to obtain a more comprehensive overview of the dynamics in the food safety problems, not only data that has direct links to food safety hazards should be collected and applied, but also data that has indirect links with food safety (e.g., trade volume, country transparency level) should be incorporated into such AI models (Liu et al., 2022).

Different types of machine learning algorithms are applied for making the predictions using the aforementioned data sources (Xinxin Wang et al., 2022; Xiyao Wang et al., 2022). Bayesian Network (BN) and Neural Network (NN) are most commonly used machine learning algorithms. BN is the most frequently used algorithm for analysing structured data and has advantage in incorporating multidimensional factors (e.g., social, environmental, economic) and expert opinions. AI models are being applied in different food safety area using BN. Just to name a few examples, 1) in the area of harmful algal blooms (HABs), BN was applied to predict the toxin concentrations in mussels using satellite data in combination with monitoring data on shellfish toxins produced by HABs (Xiyao Wang et al., 2022); 2) in the area of

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 81

mycotoxins and fungal growth, BN was used together with mechanistic model using satellite data to predict Aflatoxins in maize (Xinxin Wang et al., 2022); 3) in the area of food fraud, a BN model was developed based on adulteration/fraud notifications as reported in the Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) and was able to predict the type of food fraud notification in RASFF with high accuracy (Bouzemrak & Marvin, 2016). NN, as another most commonly used machine learning algorithm, is the main algorithm for analysing unstructured data because of its advantage of handling both image and text data. Example cases of application in the food safety domain are for instance, 1) Twitter was used as data inputs for a text mining machine learning model to predict lettuce food poisoning in the USA (Tao et al., 2021); 2) Gavai et al. (2021) has adopted a word-embedding model on data sources obtained from the European Media Monitor and scientific literature to detect unknown illegal stimulants in food supplements.

Moreover, profound progress has been made in developing smart food safety EWS using AI and ML. A real-time food fraud EWS was developed by Marvin et al. (2022) using media reports collected from all over the world through the tool MediSys-FF (Bouzemrak et al., 2018). In addition, an automated food safety EWS in the dairy supply chain was developed by Liu et al. (2022) using machine learning for real-time anomaly detection for food authorities and inspectors. The emergence of such smart systems enables decision-makers to capture signals that precede the development of a food safety risk by monitoring the drivers of change in the food system. The successful implementation of the smart food safety EWS allows real-time anomaly detection for all actors along the food supply chain, which facilitates the proactive prediction of food safety hazards, and enhances the resilience of food supply chain to food safety risks (Liu et al., 2022).

Liu et al. (2022) detected anomalies in indicator data expected by domain experts to impact the development of food safety risks in milk, by using dynamic unsupervised anomaly detection models. Additionally, chemical food safety hazards in milk associated with an anomaly for the Netherlands were identified by using a Bayesian network. Geng et al. (2017) also select indicators which can directly affect the safety of dairy products. Then the Analytic hierarchy process is used to extract the features of the input parameters and reduce data dimensions. Then extreme learning machine is used to predict dairy products safety risks. The proposed method is applied to the food safety early warning and monitoring system in China. Gawlik-Kobylińska et al. (2021) propose using machine learning, modelling algorithms and a contaminant dispersion model to combine signals from different sensors, and to reduce false alarm rates. In the proposed chemical reconnaissance (detection, identification, and monitoring) system two machine learning tasks classification and regression are used for anomaly detection and verification, respectively.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 82

6 ANNEX II: Sources of information for the PARC EWS

6.1 Sources outside PARC

6.1.1 NORMAN network

NORMAN is a non-profit, multinational association in the field of CECs in the environment. It brings together over 80 organizations from various stakeholders, including competent authorities, research centres, academia, industry, and national reference laboratories.

NORMAN organises the development and maintenance of various web-based databases for the collection & evaluation of data / information on emerging substances in the environment

- SEARCH All Databases**: Searching for individual substance or group(s) of substances in all databases. Note: Click on a link below to go to an individual database home page.
- SARS-CoV-2 in sewage**: A database with the latest information on SARS-CoV-2 in sewage across Europe and internationally, including a common protocol for sample collection, storage, extraction, analysis and data sharing to support the development of an international comparable data set.
- Substance Database**: A merged list of NORMAN substances; Central Database to access various lists of substances for suspect screening and prioritisation.
- Chemical Occurrence Data**: A database of geo-referenced monitoring data on emerging substances.
- Ecotoxicology**: A platform for systematic collection and evaluation of ecotoxicity studies for harmonised derivation of environmental quality standards.
- Suspect List Exchange**: Central Database to access various lists of substances for suspect screening and prioritisation.
- Antibiotic Resistance Bacteria/Genes**: A database of ARBs/ARGs in environmental matrices.
- MassBank Europe**: A database of mass spectra of emerging substances to support identification of unknown substances.
- Digital Sample Freezing Platform**: A database of mass chromatograms obtained by LC-HR-MS for retrospective screening of environmental samples.
- Indoor Environment**: A database of data in indoor environment matrices.
- Passive Sampling**: A database of data obtained with passive samplers.
- Substance Factsheets**: A summary information on individual substances from all NORMAN Database System modules.
- Prioritisation**: Results of prioritisation of NORMAN substances using the NORMAN Prioritisation Framework.
- Bioassays Monitoring Data**: A database of data obtained by analysis of environmental samples with bioassays.

Figure 10. Screenshot of the NORMAN Database System (NDS). The website is available at <https://www.norman-network.com/nds/>.

NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.net/>) is mostly based in Europe, but it also has a presence in North America and Asia. It aggregates high-level, multidisciplinary expertise and has developed its own Database System (NDS). NDS is an open-access platform of interconnected databases that can assist in the effective and rapid screening and risk assessment of contaminants in the environment. It brings together, in a single platform, widely differing chemical monitoring data acquired using various techniques and in different matrices, thereby ensuring a harmonised approach for data collection, storage, quality control, curation and exchange among NORMAN members and more widely. The NDS

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 83

currently consists of 13 modules (**Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**), of which 12 (Substance Database (SusDat); Suspect List Exchange (SLE); Chemical Occurrence Data (EMPODAT); Ecotoxicology; Bioassays Monitoring Data; MassBank Europe; Digital Sample Freezing Platform (DSFP); Indoor Environment; Passive Sampling; Substance Factsheets; Prioritisation) are accessible, interlinked and populated with data.

Harmonised list of chemical compounds shared among all parties in research and regulation is one critical requirement for enhanced cooperation among existing regulatory frameworks and shifting towards a “one chemical, one assessment” paradigm. The **SLE database** aims to tackle the current status in which the chemicals lists are fragmented collections, with researchers and regulators all using their own lists. By acting as a data collector, the NORMAN SLE has become an important source of specialised research information for major chemical databases such as PubChem and CompTox, beyond the realms and means of individual researchers.

The **SusDat** database is the merged master list of compounds. It is a curated compound database, where substances are merged by the Standard InChIKey, which acts as the unique identifier. This is accompanied by other structural information such as CAS numbers and SMILES, physicochemical properties, MS Ready SMILES, well as other mass spectrometric information for the identification of compounds with NTS techniques.

The **Ecotoxicology Database** is used to evaluate the reliability and relevance of ecotoxicity studies and reach consensus on Quality Standards (i.e., PNEC values) for a more harmonised risk assessment of chemicals. The database provides a transparent tool to guide experts in: (i) the identification of the reliable ecotoxicity studies, based on the CRED (Criteria for Reporting and Evaluating ecotoxicity Data) classification system. At present the database comprises, for almost all SusDat substances at least one *in silico* PNEC based on predicted acute effects for each of the three basic trophic levels of the freshwater compartment (fish, daphnia, and *algae*).

The **Chemical Occurrence Database** (EMPODAT) has been a game changer for next generation chemical risk assessment. It is a system able to provide comprehensive information on the exposure of humans and the environment to large numbers of chemicals during the entire life cycle of products, including waste and recycled products. EMPODAT today hosts approximately 95.7 million geo-referenced target monitoring data of more than 4500 substances in water (surface, ground, and wastewater), sediment, biota, soil, sewage sludge and air matrices. The data are publicly accessible and provide an overview of benchmark values on the occurrence of CECs across Europe.

The **Digital Sample Freezing Platform** is a key tool developed by NORMAN to support suspect and non-target screening. This novel technology allows the storage of thousands of high-resolution mass spectra (fingerprints) of all chemicals, metabolites and transformation

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 84

products detected in each of the analysed samples. Thanks to this platform, it is possible for users to search retrospectively for a large number of compounds (e.g., those in SusDat) in all the “digitally frozen” samples stored in the database and obtain reliable qualitative and semi-quantitative data on their occurrence in the investigated samples.

The NORMAN database gathers lots of different chemical info, helping to quickly check for risks. It serves as a useful tool for an EWS that can swiftly identify and respond to new chemical hazards.

6.1.2 RIVM/ECHA work on NERCs

The work of the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) and ECHA on NERCs can play a critical role in an EWS for chemical risk and the work that Task 8.2 envisions (Palmen, 2016). At the same time, it can carry out risk assessments identifying potential risks to health and the environment and inform the ones that are responsible for risk management. In addition, through RIVM/ECHA the use and presence of NERCs in the environment can be monitored, providing early warning of potential risks. All exported information on exposure levels estimates risk and management measures on NERCs and can be shared with competent authorities and stakeholders. Finally, RIVM/ECHA can provide recommendations and guidance on risk management measures for NERCs, including controls on their production, use and disposal (Palmen, 2016).

By integrating the work of RIVM/ECHA on NERCs into an EWS for chemical risk at EU level under PARC, relevant authorities can receive timely and accurate information on new and emerging substances, allowing them to take appropriate action to minimize harm.

6.1.3 EFSA's Emerging Risk Exchange Network (EREN)

The successful identification of risks at their early inception is important for the protection of the public health. According to the Founding Regulation of EFSA (Regulation (EC) 178/2002) one of the Agency tasks is the establishment of a system of networks of organisations operating in the fields within its mission. The Regulation also foresees that EFSA shall act in close cooperation with the competent bodies in the Member States that carry out similar tasks and where appropriate with the relevant agencies of the European Union. In this context an Emerging Risk Exchange Network (EREN) was established in 2010. Under the current Terms of Reference (revised in December 2021) (EFSA, 2021), the role of the network is ‘to provide a platform for the scientific cooperation between risk assessors of the EU Member States, EFSA the European Commission and observers from other interested parties to assess newly identified emerging issues/risks and to enhance emerging risk identification methodologies’.

The term emerging risk is defined as a risk to human, animal, plant health and the environment resulting from a new hazard or increased susceptibility or exposure to an existing known hazard (EFSA, 2007). This definition encompasses the context of novelty, of a new hazard or of a re-emerging hazard under new conditions. The challenges in emerging risks arise from the uncertainty on their potential consequences and/or probabilities of occurrence, the lack of data and the difficulty to quantify the

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 85

risk. Before the identification of an emerging risk, a signal and then an emerging issue is recognised that could be caused by different drivers e.g., new epidemiological evidence, new consumption trend, climate change.

Members of EREN are expected to contribute in different ways on the identification of emerging risks, such as presentation of information on newly identified emerging issues, risks or drivers from their activities at local level; provision of support to EFSA in the characterization and prioritization of identified emerging risks; suggestions on follow up actions; and provision of additional data on issues discussed in past EREN meetings. EREN meetings are held twice annually, where signals brought from the members are discussed. Recommendations for collection of more data, for further research needs, for joint projects among EREN members and communication with the EC are potential follow up actions of the discussions.

In addition to EREN, EFSA holds a Stakeholder Discussion Group on Emerging Risks (STADG-ER), in order to benefit from the knowledge that stakeholder specialists have in the identification of new or emerging issues. This group also contributes to the identification and characterisation of emerging risks in food and feed chain, as well as plant and animal health in Europe. A linkage between the STADG-ER and EREN is established, activities of one's network are presented to the other, and joint meetings are scheduled in order to collect expert advice.

Advantages from this exchange platform of EFSA is the promotion of collaborations among Member States, and the avoidance of duplication of work between EFSA and Member States to a certain extent.

The work of EREN and STADG-ER has confidentiality restrictions. However, brief minutes on the agenda items of the meetings are available in EFSA's web page. All emerging signals, issues and risks identified are stored in EFSA's repository. Currently a new platform as a single web-application hosted by EFSA that is supposed to facilitate the exchange between different stakeholder groups, is under development from EFSA.

6.1.4 Human biomonitoring data

6.1.4.1 General

Human biomonitoring is the measurement of different chemicals in the form of the parent compounds, their metabolites or their reaction products in human tissues and fluids. The main matrices that are being used in human biomonitoring measurements are blood, serum, plasma, urine, hair, cord blood, breast milk, amniotic fluid, placenta, meconium, semen, exhaled air, saliva, nails, deciduous teeth and sweat (World Health Organization, 2015). Biomonitoring measurements are referred to different types of biomarkers such as biomarkers of exposure, biomarkers of effect, biomarkers of susceptibility and "Omics" biomarkers for research and discovery. Further, biomonitoring data represents exposure from multiple sources. This includes indoor and outdoor air, soil, dust, water, food and/or potential exposures from products used frequently by consumers, such as cosmetics and health products. Biomonitoring data also incorporates exposures from all routes (oral, dermal and inhalation).

Human biomonitoring is being carried out through HBM surveys. These surveys in EU are mainly national HBM programs, i.e., Germany (Schulz et al., 2007), Belgium (Flemish region) (Schoeters et al.,

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 86

2017), France (Dereumeaux et al., 2017), Czech Republic (Cerna et al., 2012), Sweden (Berglund, 2015), and Slovenia (Stajniko et al., 2020) but the last years, in the frame of different projects like COPHES, DEMOCOPHES (Schindler et al., 2014) and HBM4EU (Gilles et al., 2021; Gilles et al., 2022) works as “European surveys”. HBM surveys can have several objectives, such as: assessing the distribution of exposure; detecting emerging threats; monitoring the effects of policy interventions aimed at reducing or preventing harmful exposures; setting priorities for downstream risk assessment; monitoring spatial patterns and temporal trends; identifying and monitoring contaminated sites; supporting epidemiological research; and serving the development of the “exposome” concept.

Human biomonitoring (HBM) data can be a valuable tool in an EWS by providing real-word exposure insights, aiding in risk assessment prioritization and supporting the understanding of chemical exposure.

6.1.4.2 HBM4EU

Since 2017, the German Environment Agency was coordinating the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative, which comprised 116 partner institutions from 30 country members.

As part of the HBM4EU project, the HBM4EU-aligned studies were set up to collect harmonized and quality controlled recent internal exposure data from European citizens to environmental pollutants (Gilles et al., 2021; Gilles et al., 2022). The HBM4EU-aligned studies have brought together ongoing and newly planned HBM initiatives in Europe and harmonized them. As a result, HBM4EU-aligned studies collected samples from three different age group, children (6–11 years), teenagers (12–19 years), and adults (20–39 years) that is representative of sex (males, females) including people from cities, towns/suburbs, and rural areas, with different socio-economic status (SES), and from the four geographical regions of Europe (north, east, south, and west) (Gilles et al., 2021; Gilles et al., 2022).

HBM4EU can play a key role in collecting and analysing HBM data on a large scale. This data can be integrated into an EWS for chemical risk to provide a comprehensive view of chemical exposure and health risks (HBM4EU, 2022).

6.1.5 Information Platform on Chemicals Monitoring (IPCHEM)

IPCHEM (<https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>) - the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring – serves as the reference access point for locating and retrieving chemical occurrence data across various media (e.g., environment, human, food/feed, indoor air and products) in the European Union. IPCHEM is being operated by the European Commission Services and the European Union Agencies (IPCHEM, 2018). IPCHEM is being operated by the European Commission Services and the European Union Agencies (IPCHEM, 2018).

IPCHEM supports a coordinated approach for collecting, storing, accessing, and evaluating data related to occurrence of chemicals and chemical mixtures. “This would help identify links between exposure and epidemiological data in order to explore potential biological effects and lead to improved health outcomes” as it is stated in the EC Communication “The

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 87

combination effects of chemicals – Chemical mixtures” (COM/2012/0252 final) (European Commission, 2023) .

Figure 11. IPCHEM combination of sources

IPCHEM was designed and implemented as a distributed infrastructure (web portal and related tools), providing when feasible remote access to existing chemical monitoring data. In parallel, it offers data hosting capacities if requested by Data Providers/Data Owners.

By providing real-time information on chemical substances in the environment, IPCHEM can help improve the overall efficiency and effectiveness of an EWS for chemical risk.

6.1.6 Monitoring in polar regions

Systematic monitoring programmes in the Arctic were established in the early 1990s, in response to increasing evidence that POPs, mercury and other environmental pollutants, such as radionuclides, accumulated in the Arctic (AMAP assessment report, 1998). Although emitted far away from the Arctic, POPs and other pollutants are sufficiently persistent to be transported to the Arctic, to accumulate in Arctic food webs and to cause exposure of local and Indigenous communities relying on Arctic animals for their diet.

The monitoring programmes have generated time series of pollutants in biota and air that meet several purposes: i) monitor the effectiveness of regulations, such as those of the UN Stockholm Convention, ii) identify emerging issues, such as increasing concentrations of non-regulated chemicals, iii) determine pollutant levels in animals that are part of the traditional diet and iv) provide evidence for long-range transport and/or bioaccumulation for risk assessments under the Stockholm Convention. Time series from individual Arctic countries are combined and assessed in a circumpolar perspective under the auspices of the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme, to improve our understanding of Arctic pollution and the global fate of these contaminants (Rigét et al., 2019; Wong et al., 2021).

The biota contaminant monitoring programme in Greenland includes biannual sampling campaigns where all samples are stored in an Environmental Specimen Bank (Rigét et al., 2016). This provides

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 88

opportunities for retrospective time trends (Vorkamp et al., 2011) and screening studies (Vorkamp et al., 2015), both important elements of an EWS. Recently, influences of climate change have been documented for the long-term time series from the Arctic (Vorkamp et al., 2022).

Unlike the Arctic, the Antarctic does not have a systematic and coordinated monitoring programme, but an Antarctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AnMAP) has been proposed after the AMAP model (Nash, 2011). Nevertheless, contaminant studies are being conducted in the Antarctic and provide additional evidence of persistence and long-range transport for the compounds detected far away from emission sources (Corsolini et al., 2006).

The monitoring program in the Arctic, examining persistent pollutants and long-range transport, can contribute valuable data for the EWS. These initiatives help assess regulations, identify emerging issues, and provide evidence crucial for risk assessments.

6.1.7 European Environmental Agency

The responsibility of EEA (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en>) is the provision of timely, targeted, relevant, reliable and independent information on the environment to policy makers and the public. At this moment, 32 member countries and 6 cooperating countries compose the EEA. The first group of partners consists of: the 27 European Union Member States, together with Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland and Turkey. The 6 cooperating countries include: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, as well as Kosovo (*without prejudice to positions on status, and in line with UNSCR 1244 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo Declaration of Independence*). As far as it concerns the former member country of United Kingdom, EEA products, websites and services may refer to research carried out prior to the UK's withdrawal from the EU.

Possessing the data, EEA supports all the above countries to make informed decisions about improving the environment, integrating environmental considerations into economic policies and moving towards sustainability. Moreover, in collaboration with a broad range of external authors and peer reviewers, EEA provides occasionally reports of late lessons from early warnings focus on occupational, public health and environmental hazards (EEA, 2001) (EEA, 2013). EEA develops and coordinates the European environment information and observation network (Eionet) together with National Focal Points (NFPs), which are appointed institutions of each country, and centres of thematic expertise contracted by the EEA called European Topic Centres (ETCs) (EIONET, 2023). Eionet is a useful partnership network for EWS as it is characterized by a) strong institutional cooperation across national, regional, European, and international levels and partnerships with civil society, facilitated by a coordinating entity, b) agreed common content- data, information, indicators, analysis and c) shared infrastructure, standards and tools.

6.1.8 National monitoring networks

Each individual country has its own national monitoring network approach which aligns with the comprehensive approach of the EWS for detecting and responding to potential risks. For environmental monitoring this can be driven by requirements as set out by the Water

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 89

Framework Directive, including Watch List processes. However, there is frequently more extensive monitoring for emerging substances, than is required in statute. This includes specific programmes to better understand general exposure, as well as targeted approaches to understand specific chemical sources.

6.1.9 National food authorities

National Food Authorities (NFAs) have as primary mission to protect the consumers' health and interests ensuring food safety across the production and supply chain and they are responsible to ensure the compliance of the FBOs with the EU and national legislation.

NFAs carry out official controls and especially national monitoring programmes in order to survey the occurrence of food contaminants either from environment or by migration from food contact materials and articles (FCMs). They also participate in monitoring programmes in collaboration with other Member-States initiated and coordinated by the European Commission.

NFAs conduct inspections in Food and FCM enterprises along the supply chain (production, processing, distribution and marketing) of food and FCMs products. Moreover, they are responsible to inform consumers about the outcomes of their control/monitoring activities concerning any food safety issues. An important task of the NFA arising from the General Food Law (Reg. (EU) 178/2002) is the implementation of risk assessment for all food safety hazards.

Furthermore, NFAs participate in research programmes and networks relevant to food safety, collaborating closely with academia. The recognition of emerging risks is one among their tasks.

In order to ensure human health protection, NFAs collaborate closely with other national relevant authorities such as Ministries of Agriculture, Ministry of Health, Ministry of Environment Protection, Risk Assessment and Research Institutes, General State Chemical Laboratories for the best coordination and effectiveness of official controls in the food chain.

NFAs collaborate with European Authorities (European Commission, Council of Europe, ECHA, and EFSA) or International Organizations (FAO/WHO) on key issues concerning food safety and the determination of food standards. NFAs participate in several expert working groups of the Council of Europe and the European Commission. NFAs are regularly the official national contact points of RASFF, EFSA and FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius. NFAs also participate in the Food Fraud Network (FFN) and the Administrative Assistance and Cooperation (AAC) System of the EC.

Specifically, NFAs work closely with EFSA by participating in EFSA's Advisory Forum and scientific networks for efficient risk assessment and risk communication, including data

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 90

collection. These collaborations can help identify emerging risks and weak signals, contributing to the EWS.

6.1.10 Social media

Social media platforms including X (twitter), Facebook, and alike could provide valuable information where potential new chemical threats are being discussed on new use of chemicals, new products, effects, and occurrence in various human and environmental samples. Data from social media has great potential as it could provide real-time information with geospatial and demographic resolution. In addition, social media could contribute to identifying trends or emerging risks, by providing information not only on actual use, but also of misuse of, and exposure to, chemicals. However, such data requires elaborate and careful treatment using natural language processing to handle issues of bias, reliability, etc.

6.2 Sources inside PARC

6.2.1 WP2 on prioritization

"PARCopedia", which is developed and maintained under WP2, could act as an information exchange forum regarding emerging chemical risks and information on uses and exposure. In addition, "PARCopedia" will ensure links between research activities and regulatory needs, and "PARCroute", which is the long-term strategic roadmap, will ensure the sustainability of PARC results and outputs after seven years. These frameworks will support both the scientific excellence of the PARC EWS, as well as its link with the relevant regulatory actors.

6.2.2 WP3 by SF and IB consultation and synergies outside PARC

WP3 will facilitate the interaction of the PARC EWS with relevant stakeholders through the Stakeholder Forum, while critical input for the framework will be provided by the International Board. In addition, data and methods could be introduced by interactions with scientific networks and external collaborations, synergies and projects under the auspices of WP3.

6.2.3 WP4 on environmental, HBM and exposure data

WP4 will contribute with advancing the methods for identifying emerging chemical exposure signatures by (a) continuation of the HBM4EU-established human biomonitoring platform, (b) establishment of an EU-wide environmental and multisource monitoring, and (c) continued development of cutting-edge monitoring techniques and tools.

6.2.4 WP5 on hazard assessment

The work carried on in the framework of WP5 will provide signals on potential hazards from chemicals, thus, focusing on the identification of new information about the intrinsic hazard properties of the chemicals, taking stock of the latest advances related to NAMs, mechanism of toxicity identification and the development of new adverse outcome pathways.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 91

6.2.5 WP6 on risk estimates and IATA

Work carried out in WP6 relevant to aggregate exposure and PBPK modelling for lifelong exposure, will support the EWS by providing tools that facilitate signal amplification. In addition risk assessment methods developed in WP6 will support the risks prioritisation.

6.2.6 WP7 on available data and analyses

Work in WP7 will ensure the FAIRness of data used within the EWS; data “FAIRification” is a crucial point for the implementation of EWS due to the fact that it should be continuously fed with data. This will cover a broad range of approaches that will be developed and documented, including pooling and meta-analysis of heterogeneous datasets, uncertainty analysis, and knowledge and text mining via on-the-fly ontological mapping, Bayesian networks and machine learning. EWS will take advantage of these algorithms in order to analyse large amounts of data, extract pieces of information from the available literature and evaluate the uncertainty of the methods used.

6.2.7 WP8 on computational methods (Task 8.3)

With links to the EWS and models from other projects, this task aims to integrate the models created and the data that will be gathered and generated within PARC into a comprehensive and unified framework. It then implements this in a functional and open PARC computational tool network infrastructure. In the framework of Task 8.2, Task 8.3 will contribute to almost all computational tiers as they are presented in the modelling tools section. The network infrastructure that will be implemented is illustrated in the **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** and consists of several novel modelling tools that can contribute effectively to EWS, facilitating the amplification process.

D8.2: Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	Dissemination level: PU
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 1.0
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis	Page: 92